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**Mixed Precision Multigrid Methods
on Hybrid Tetrahedral Grids**

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Master's Thesis

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Abstract

The goal of this thesis is the accurate and performant implementation of mixed precision for the HPC FE framework HyTeG. In scientific computing, it is common to use single or double precision for computations. Lowering the precision reduces runtime and energy consumption but results in less reliable approximations. Mixed precision has been gaining attention by addressing this trade-off. In machine learning, mixed precision focusing on low-precision computations like float16 or 8 bit is common practice, but there are various other fields in the scientific computing community where mixed precision is applied.

Building on the existing theory of Higham [1–3], Tamstorf [4–6], and Kohl [6–10], the mixed precision algorithm IR is implemented for HyTeG. The steps taken to extend the framework to support mixed precision, including the use of float16 are outlined within this thesis. Furthermore, the mixed precision implementation is validated through numerical experiments. The performance achievable by reducing the solver precision without compromising accuracy is reviewed by comparing the experimental results to those of a reliable fixed precision method.

The results suggest that mixed precision has the potential to significantly enhance the performance of existing simulations when applied appropriately.

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Motivation & Contributions

Motivation In scientific computing, employing a consistent precision for all computations is common practice. Typically, this precision is set at either single or double. Due to the extensive energy requirements of HPC systems, focusing on energy-efficient data structures becomes crucial. In addition, the performance of scientific computing tasks is frequently constrained by the data transfer required for each computation [11]. Both issues can be addressed by lowering the precision for computations [12, 13].

While using lower precision data types reduces runtime and energy consumption, it generally results in less reliable approximations [2]. Thus, most use cases require high-precision computation to produce an adequate approximation. To address this trade-off between accuracy and performance by varying the applied precision, mixed precision is steadily gaining attention in research.

Especially in the field of machine learning, where training networks requires a significant amount of time and energy [14, 15], using low-precision computations with half [16–19] (float16) or even 8 bit [20] precision is already common practice. The use of float16 and mixed precision has proven to be beneficial for other fields of research as well [21, 22]. The growing interest in float16 has led hardware manufacturers to expand their range of architectures supporting low precision formats [16, 19, 20], even for CPUs [23].

Overview The primary objective of this thesis is to implement a mixed precision algorithm for the HPC FE framework HyTeG [7] and compare its accuracy and precision to a reliable fixed precision one.

The fundamental basics for following the thesis’s discussion are given in chapter 2. It includes a description of precision for floating point [1, 24, 25], a definition for accuracy [1, 4], an introduction to the used framework [7–9], FEs [26–28] and MG [29–31], and lastly, an explanation about the differences between fixed precision and mixed precision [2–6, 21]. Chapter 3 presents an overview of the design choices of the implementations, the difficulties of realizing them, and how the final result can be applied. Finally, the mixed precision implementation is tested by solving a PDE and comparing the outcome to an existing fixed precision solver implementation in chapter 4.

Contributions

As there is much literature about the relation between precision and accuracy using mixed precision [4, 6], this thesis focuses on the accurate and performant implementation of mixed precision MG for HyTeG.

Implementations In terms of implementation, the HPC FE framework HyTeG and its associated code generator HOG have been expanded to support mixed precision. Involved steps, for generalizing existing codes are outlined in section 3.1. As the operator generator HOG provides an interfaces for the least disruptive implementation of mixed precision, a generic type class that offers optimal support for HOG's underlying backend has been developed and integrated into the code generator; including correctness tests for generating type operators. Typed operators now allow for a correct utilization of mixed precision by using the newly implemented IR algorithm which is described in section 2.5.2.

For cases where even float64 is inadequate (section 2.4) the use of the floating point emulation library MPFR [32] for HyTeG was explored.

Instead, to enhance performance of the mixed precision extension, investigations and experiments of software and hardware requirements for float16 are conducted.

Furthermore, efforts are made to generalize the MPI interface for HyTeG's backend to allow for the use of float16 on distributed systems (section 3.1.3). With the newly designed concept of handling custom MPI types, it is now possible to use not only float16 but also other data types, such as custom ones like MPFR types, with minimal extensions to the existing codebase (section 3.1.3). Finally, HyTeG now supports the use of float16, and correctness has been tested with CI tests for the framework. Users are also notified through adjustments to cmake whether the used compiler supports float16.

Numerical Experiments In the subsequent phase, the accuracy of implemented mixed precision features for HyTeG is evaluated by solving a Poisson Equation (chapter 4). The mixed precision implementations are compared to reliable fixed precision ones, with the research of Tamstorf et al. [4] (section 2.5.3) in mind.

Finally, the performance impact of mixed precision is examined. Contrary to the expectation, no performance improvement utilizing a lower solver precision is found. The source for the unexpected performance outcome could be explained by hierarchically profiling the experimental setup.

Based on the results, an estimation for the possible performance outcome of the current mixed precision implementation is made from an optimistic perspective, suggesting that when adequately applied, mixed precision can significantly enhance the performance of existing simulations.

Goal of this thesis is to investigate the achievable performance increase in HyTeG, by reducing the precision of applied method without compromising accuracy.

This chapter covers the theoretical basics necessary for understanding the vocabulary and assumptions made within this thesis.

2.1 Precision

Precision refers to the number of bits used for floating point arithmetic [1].

This number is directly correlated with the number of bits k used to represent a floating point number. A number stored with k bits has a p bits significand and computations are performed in p bit precision. To fully understand this sentence, the floating point representation used within this work is presented.

2.1.1 Floating point numbers

This section introduces the basics of numerical computation in computer systems according to Higham [1], Goldberg [24], by defining the IEEE 754 [25] floating point representation.

The numerical representation of a value consists of a finite amount of numbers. For integers ($a \in \mathbb{Z}$), exact representation with a finite amount of digits is usually possible. Representing real-valued numbers ($x \in \mathbb{R}$) is more challenging. Most of them have an infinite decimal or fractional representation. This finite representation of real numbers is called a floating point number.

As depicted in fig. 2.1, a k bit floating point number is split up into three different parts: the sign with one bit, the exponent with w bits, and the trailing significand with t bits. It is called trailing significand (S) since the most significant digit is implicitly assumed. Therefore, an additional bit for the significand (s) is gained without the need to store it explicitly.

Figure 2.1: Binary interchange floating-point format according to IEEE 754 [25]. The values w , and t stand for the number bits used to store the exponent (E), and trailing significand (S).

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	float16	float32	float64
Storage size	k	bit	16	32	64
Precision	p	bit	11	24	53
Exponent size	w	bit	5	8	11
Min exponent	e_{\min}		-14	-126	-1022
Max exponent	e_{\max}		15	127	1023
Min (subnormal) magnitude	$ \tilde{x}_{\min} $		5.96e-8	1.4e-45	5e-324
Min (normal) magnitude	$ x_{\min} $		6.10e-5	1.18e-38	2e-308
Max (normal) magnitude	$ x_{\max} $		65504	3e38	1e308
Rounding machine epsilon	ϵ_M		4.88e-04	5.96e-08	1.11e-16

Table 2.1: Key values [1, 25] of float16, float32 and float64.

The main advantage of the IEEE 754 conform binary floating point formats is their unique encoding for every machine. Independent of the hardware, all floating point numbers are stored and computed with each other in the same way to guarantee deterministic floating point computations independent of the executing machine.

The decoding of a number x is $x = \pm s \cdot 2^{e-p}$ with the significand s , the exponent e , and the precision p [1]. Possible values for the significand (s) are *significand* $\in \{0, \dots, 2^p - 1\}$ [1]. The highest exponent is $e_{\max} = 2(w - 1) - 1$ while the lowest exponent is $e_{\min} = 1 - e_{\max} = 2 - 2(w - 1)$ [25]. The value of the exponent can be $e \in \{e_{\min}, \dots, e_{\max}\}$. The exponent is also called biased exponent [25]; $e = 0$ is reserved for the value zero and subnormal numbers; e_{\max} is reserved for special values like infinity or NaN; the rest of the exponent range is used for normal numbers. Normal- and subnormal numbers are explained in section 2.1.2. The range of normal floating point numbers is $2^{e_{\min}} \leq |x| \leq 2^{e_{\max}}(2 - 2^{1-p})$ [25, p. 18]. The smallest subnormal number is $|\tilde{x}_{\min}| = 2^{e_{\min}}2^{1-p}$ [25, p. 18]. Other than for integers, the range of floating point numbers is symmetric around zero.

The most important values for the floating point number used in this thesis¹ can be found in table 2.1.

¹There exist prominent non IEEE 754 conform floating point representations as well; e.g., `bfloat16` from Google, `TensorFloat` from NVidia, or `fp24` from AMD.

Figure 2.2: Visual representation of a fictional floating point format, to illustrate the increasing spacing between numbers of different exponent and the underflow gap between zero and the smallest normal number x_{\min} .

Figure 2.3: Visual representation of a fictional floating point format, including the subnormal numbers.

2.1.2 Machine precision ϵ_M

The distance between any two adjacent numbers can be described by the machine epsilon (ϵ_M) [1]. It is defined by the distance between the number one and the next larger floating point number, for a binary formats ϵ_M is defined in eq. (2.1).

$$\epsilon_M = 2^{1-t} \quad (2.1)$$

Equation (2.1) holds for the spacing of every number between 1 and 2. When increasing of the exponent, this spacing changes by the factor of the base, i.e., a factor of two for binary systems. So, between the numbers 2 and 4, the spacing is $\epsilon_M(e = 1) = 2 \cdot 2^{1-t}$; between 1 and 0.5 the spacing is $\epsilon_M(e = -1) = 2^{-1} \cdot 2^{1-t}$. That means that the spacing of numbers with the same exponent is uniform, but changing the exponent also changes the spacing. As a consequence, floating point numbers are not uniformly distributed within the entire domain. Their distribution is visualized in fig. 2.2.

Generally, the distance Δx between each number is at maximum $\Delta x \leq \epsilon_M |x|$. When representing a real number — with a magnitude smaller than x_{\max} and larger than x_{\min} — as floating point number, the worst representational error (section 2.2.1) possible is half the distance between the next smaller and larger floating point number (eq. (2.2)).

$$e_{\text{rep}} \leq \frac{1}{2} |x| \epsilon_M \quad (2.2)$$

As can be seen from fig. 2.2, the distance between the smallest normal number and zero can be larger than this prediction. To close this so-called **underflow gap**, IEEE 754 defines subnormal numbers. As shown in fig. 2.3, these numbers fill the underflow gap with exactly t values; i.e., the gap between them is precisely as large as for the smallest normal number $\Delta x_{\min} = 2^{e_{\min}-1} \epsilon_M$.

That means when using IEEE 754 conform machines, the maximal relative error that can be made representing a real number as a floating point number is given by eq. (2.3).

$$\frac{e_{\text{rep}}}{|x|} \leq \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_M = \frac{1}{2} 2^{1-t} \quad (2.3)$$

This property is advantageous for making error predictions. It is often also referred to as `unit roundoff` or `rounding machine epsilon`.

For simplicity, from this point on, the unit roundoff is referred to as machine epsilon ϵ_M for the rest of this thesis. In chapter 4, the machine epsilon is used to give a relation between precision and accuracy.

2.2 Accuracy

Accuracy is a metric for the error coming from an approximation [1].

2.2.1 Types of Errors

The composition of the total error is not always uniformly defined in the literature. Therefore, this section considers the error sources of numerical computations and gives an appropriate vocabulary for those. The vocabulary and definition used for each error is mainly adopted from Tamstorf et al. [4], except for those generally referred to as rounding errors.

When solving mathematical problems using numerical methods, various parts of this process will introduce their own error. These errors add to a total error. Since improving one part of the process reduces a specific inaccuracy and usually leaves the other unaffected or even increases them instead, there will always be some more dominant errors along the way that influence the current accuracy stronger than others. These are referred to as leading error terms. To demonstrate the influence of each error, eq. (2.4) is a model problem that will be adjusted according to the prominent inaccuracy for each subsection.

$$\boldsymbol{v} \mapsto 2.5 \sin(\boldsymbol{v}) \sin(5\boldsymbol{v}) \cos(0.4\boldsymbol{v}) \quad \boldsymbol{v} \in [x_1, x_{10}] \quad (2.4)$$

Furthermore, to mathematically define the following error terms a general representation of a problem defined in eq. (2.5) is used.

$$\begin{aligned} A(\boldsymbol{u}) &= \boldsymbol{f} \\ A: \mathcal{C} &\rightarrow \mathcal{C}; \quad \boldsymbol{u}, \boldsymbol{f} \in \mathcal{C} \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Discretization Error

To solve a continuous problem numerically, it has to be projected to a discrete space. This holds true not only for differential equations but generally when evaluating continuous constructs; e.g., the model problem eq. (2.4) is projected onto the n -dimensional vector space \mathbb{K}^n (eq. (2.6)) and the general problem changes from eq. (2.5)

Figure 2.4: Visual representation of the inaccuracy coming from discretization, by visualizing the exact model problem (eq. (2.4)) in blue and the exact solution of the discretized model problem (eq. (2.6)) in orange.

to eq. (2.7).

$$\mathbf{v}_h \mapsto 2.5 \sin(\mathbf{v}_h) \sin(5\mathbf{v}_h) \cos(0.4\mathbf{v}_h) \quad \mathbf{v} \in \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{10}\} \quad (2.6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_h(\mathbf{u}_h) &= \mathbf{f}_h \\ A_h: \mathbb{K}^n &\rightarrow \mathbb{K}^n; \quad \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{f}_h \in \mathbb{K}^n \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

Equation (2.6) illustrates that the discretized model problem is solved exactly, however, the discretized problem is not the exact model problem. Therefore, the discretization error describes the right solution to almost the right problem.

The error introduced by discretization is described in eq. (2.8).

$$e_{\text{disc}} = \|\mathbf{u}_h - \mathbf{u}\| \quad (2.8)$$

The difference between eqs. (2.4) and (2.6) is visually represented in fig. 2.4, where the model problem is evaluated on a finite number of equidistant points n with a spacing of h . Therefore, the index h is a metric for the resolution of the problem.

To reduce the discretization error, the resolution h of the discretization must be improved. Either by increasing the number of points to represent the problem or by enhancing the discretization order. There exist different kinds of discretization methods, the one used for the numerical experiment in chapter 4 is described in section 2.3.1.

Representational Error

As mentioned in section 2.1, when representing a real number, only a finite amount of digits or — in the case of a computer — bits are available to do so. So, in numerics,

Figure 2.5: Visual representation of the inaccuracy coming from the floating point representation of the solution, by visualizing the exact model problem (eq. (2.4)) in blue and the model problem correctly solved and rounded to floating point precision as shown in eq. (2.9) in orange.

every real valued number is affected by rounding. Assuming a computation can be done exactly, or the target real-valued number is known and needs to be represented as a floating point number, the result is still subject to the representational error (eq. (2.10)).

$$fl(2.5 \sin(\mathbf{v}_h) \sin(5\mathbf{v}_h) \cos(0.4\mathbf{v}_h)) \quad \mathbf{v}_h \in \mathbb{K}^n \quad (2.9)$$

Viewed in a certain floating point number system, eq. (2.9) produces the exact solution of the exact problem in an inexact representational space.

How the representational error affects the solution for the model problem is depicted in fig. 2.5.

$$e_{fp} = \|fl(\mathbf{u}_h) - \mathbf{u}_h\| \quad (2.10)$$

To reduce representational error, the precision must be increased. This is usually barely possible, as for available computer systems float64 is the highest hardware supported precision to represent a number in. More information about hardware supported floating point representations can be found in sections 3.1.2 and 3.1.3.

The representational error is mentioned for completeness only, as for further discussions, it is assumed to be part of the quantization error.

Quantization Error

In reality, not only the final result of a computation is affected by the inaccuracy produced representing a floating point number, but all input values in numerical computation, as shown in eq. (2.11).

$$fl(2.5 \sin(fl(\mathbf{v})) \sin(fl(5) fl(\mathbf{v})) \cos(fl(0.4) fl(\mathbf{v}))) \quad \mathbf{v} \in [x_1, x_{10}] \quad (2.11)$$

Figure 2.6: Visual representation of the inaccuracy coming from quantization, by visualizing the exact model problem (eq. (2.4)) in blue and the exact solution of the quantized model problem (eq. (2.11)) in orange.

So when the input of a problem is affected by inaccuracies coming from the floating point representation, exactly computing the solution of the given problem $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ is still different from the actual solution \mathbf{u} . This inaccuracy is called quantization error eq. (2.12).

$$e_{\text{quant}} = \|\hat{\mathbf{u}} - \mathbf{u}\| \quad (2.12)$$

As for discretization error, it stems from computing the exact solution to almost the right problem. Other than for discretization error, this one is not limited by the number of points n available to refine the problem but by the number of values available to describe the input of the problem; i.e., the precision. Since all input values are affected by these inaccuracies, the influence of the quantization error is in general higher than the one from representational error, as visualized in fig. 2.6.

The more complex the input, the larger the impact of quantization error [4]. As for section 2.2.1, this one can only be decreased by increasing the precision. However, not all parts of a numerical solver strategy are equally affected by quantization error, as mentioned in section 2.5.

Operational Error

When actually solving a problem various numerical operations to approximate a solution are involved. Therefore, solving a problem involves many sub-operations which introduce and accumulate certain inaccuracies. Some combinations of these produced inaccuracies are more benign, while others will diminish the quality of the final approximation tremendously [1, 24].

In literature, these accumulated inaccuracies are usually referred to as rounding error. This terminology might lead to the suggestion that floating point numbers

are incorrectly rounding, which is, in fact, not the case. Rounding performed on an IEEE 754 conform machine is correct for given precision [24]. The error introduced by rounding is the representational error described in section 2.1.2. Therefore, within this work, the error typically referred to as rounding error will be called operational error. This name clarifies that this produced error is the result of accumulation of inexact numerical operations, rather than rounding [1, 24].

$$2.5 \otimes \sin(\mathbf{v}_h) \otimes \sin(5\mathbf{v}_h) \otimes \cos(0.4\mathbf{v}_h) \quad \mathbf{v}_h \in \mathbb{K}^n \quad (2.13)$$

Other than for the previously mentioned errors — i.e., discretization error, representational error, and quantization error — here, the right solution is computed in an inexact manner.

The operational error is defined as the difference between the exact solution of a given problem $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ and the solution $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h$ computed by the solver.

$$e_{\text{op}} = \|\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h - \hat{\mathbf{u}}\| \quad (2.14)$$

This error can be reduced by the application of robust algorithms, one example being the Kahan summation [1, 24]. Choosing suitable algorithms, however, is not always a trivial task as robustness usually comes at the price of performance. This tradeoff is a topic that has been extensively discussed in various literature about numerical solvers [1, 27, 31].

Iteration Error

One class of numerical solution strategies is iterative solver methods. For this thesis, a subclass of iterative solvers called MG methods [29, 30] is applied. The focus of this thesis are accuracy and performance investigations for a specific extension of MG. More information and examples of the solving behavior of MG methods can be found in the literature.

When iteratively approximating a solution, the accuracy of the approximation is increased in every step as long as iteration error is the dominant error term. The iteration error is described as the difference between the converged approximation $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h$ and the approximation after the i 'th iteration \mathbf{v}_h^i (eq. (2.15)).

$$e_{\text{it}} = \|\mathbf{v}_h^i - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h\| \quad (2.15)$$

The error reduction rate per iteration depends on the applied solver. Choosing a suitable solver for a given problem is not trivial [26, 27, 30, 31], as there is no ideal solver for every situation.

Total Error

In the end, the accuracy of a numerical approximation is described by the difference between the current approximation \mathbf{v}_h^i and the actual solution of the right problem \mathbf{u} .

This is called the total error (eq. (2.16)).

$$\begin{aligned}
 e_{\text{tot}} &= \| \mathbf{v}_h^i - \mathbf{u} \| \\
 &= \| \mathbf{v}_h^i - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h + \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h - \hat{\mathbf{u}} + \hat{\mathbf{u}} - \mathbf{u}_h + \mathbf{u}_h - \mathbf{u} \| \\
 &\leq e_{\text{it}} + e_{\text{op}} + e_{\text{quant}} + e_{\text{disc}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.16}$$

When reformulating eq. (2.16) to include the errors coming from all sub-steps of a numerical solution process, and applying the triangle inequality, an upper limit for the total error can be given which is the sum of all individual errors.

From here on out, the total error is referred to as error. It will be explicitly named if a more specific kind of inaccuracy is of interest.

Algebraic Error

The iteration error is a metric to describe how far the iterative application of a solver has converged already, and the operational error is a result of repeated accumulation of inaccuracies during the application of one such solver. Together, these two error metrics describe the general accuracy of the applied solver method. Since for this work, the solver of interest is given, and only the current quality of the solution is of interest, both error terms are considered into the error of the solver, named algebraic error (eq. (2.17)), for further discussion. To consider these two error as one is not uncommon; e.g., Tamstorf et al. [4].

$$e_{\text{alg}} = e_{\text{it}} + e_{\text{op}} \tag{2.17}$$

When the algebraic error is reduced well enough, the approximation describes almost the right solution to nearly the right problem. The model problem (eq. (2.4)) described at the beginning of this section is visualized in fig. 2.7, under the assumption that the algebraic error is reduced until it becomes negligible compared to discretization error and quantization error,

Residual

For non-textbook problems, the exact solution is unknown; therefore, the error cannot be computed directly. In practice, the residual is often used to measure the quality of the current solution. The residual is a metric that describes the difference between the left-hand and right-hand sides of a given numeric problem (eq. (2.18)).

$$\mathbf{r}_h = \mathbf{f}_h - A_h \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h \tag{2.18}$$

Since the given problem is already subject to quantization and discretization, it is more accurate to say that it indicates algebraic error, rather than the total error.

These are the definitions of the numerical error used for further discussion. Other definitions, examples, and explanations of the error can be found in literature [1, 4, 5, 27–30].

Figure 2.7: Visual representation of the inaccuracy coming from solving an inaccurate problem, by visualizing the exact model problem (eq. (2.4)) in blue and the exact solution of almost the right model problem affected by quantization and discretization (eqs. (2.6) and (2.11)) in orange.

2.2.2 Norms

As a metric for accuracy, norms are used to measure the error (e) and the residual (r_h). As mentioned in section 2.2.1, solving a continuous problem numerically requires discretization. When using a FE (section 2.3.1) discretization, variables are sometimes denoted as elements of a suitable vector space \mathbf{V} and sometimes as values on the grid Ω_h . Depending on the type of value, different metrics are utilized.

Norm to measure the Accuracy

For all function values in the FE space, the L^2 -norm [27, Ch. 2] is used.

$$\|v\|_{L^2} = \left(\int_{\Omega} v^2 \right)^{1/2} \quad (2.19)$$

The norm described in eq. (2.19) is used to compute a measure for the error as well as for the exact solution on the discretized domain u_h . Since numerically the integral cannot be determined exactly, a fifth order quadrature [27] is used to approximate the integral².

Discrete Norm used for Runtime Control

For some quantities the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm (eq. (2.20)) is used as measure instead of the computational costly L^2 -norm. This is the case for the residual r_h in general, as

²Dokumentation for the L^2 space approximation can be found in the HyTeG documentation at https://hyteg.pages.i10git.cs.fau.de/hyteg/classhyteg_1_1L2Space.html

well as for the error when used as stopping criteria for the solver as in section 4.3. discretized as values on the grid Ω_h to be used .

$$\|\mathbf{v}_h\|_{\tilde{l}^2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \mathbf{v}_h \cdot \mathbf{v}_h} \quad (2.20)$$

Relative Norms used for Comparison

To compare computed measures relatively, two relative norms are defined for function-valued elements and vector-valued points. These are defined by the absolute norm, scaled by the norm of a relative quantity $\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}}\|$.

For the error in the FE space, the norm of the exact solution $\mathbf{v}_{\text{ref}} := \mathbf{u}$ is used as a reference to compare the error against machine epsilon ϵ_M .

$$\frac{\|\mathbf{e}\|_{L^2}}{\|\mathbf{e}_{\text{ref}}\|_{L^2}} = \frac{e_{\text{tot}}}{\|\mathbf{u}\|_{L^2}} \quad (2.21)$$

For the values at a certain grid point, the reference quantity is the initial guess of the quantity ($\mathbf{v}_{h,\text{ref}} := \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h^{(0)}$). The initial value is chosen to illustrate the change per iteration i independently of the current refinement level l .

$$\frac{\|\mathbf{v}_h\|_{\tilde{l}^2}}{\|\mathbf{v}_{h,\text{ref}}\|_{\tilde{l}^2}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{v}_h^{(i)}\|_{\tilde{l}^2}}{\|\mathbf{v}_h^{(0)}\|_{\tilde{l}^2}} \quad (2.22)$$

2.3 Fundamentals description of HyTeG

The goal of this thesis is to investigate performance from a mixed precision approach in comparison to a fixed precision one. Before doing so, the fundamentals for defining the problem and the approximation strategy are described in this section.

2.3.1 Model Problem

To examine performance and accuracy, a Poisson Equation [27, Ch. 1] is chosen as model problem. Its formulation is given in eq. (2.23).

$$-\Delta \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f} \quad (2.23)$$

This model problem is a second order PDE.

The Finite Element Method

The problem is discretized using Lagrangian FE of first (\mathbb{P}_1) and second (\mathbb{P}_2) order [6, 10]. There is ample literature in this field, such as the books from Strang [26], Großmann [27], and Elman [28].

All values \mathbf{v} are element of a suitable vector space \mathbf{V} , while the specific values at point of grid Ω_h are represented by \mathbf{v}_h .

The weak formulation resulting from this discretization is given in eq. (2.24).

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \phi \quad (2.24)$$
$$\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{f}, \phi \in \mathbf{V}$$

Großmann [27, Ch. 3] describes how a weak formulation is formed.

According to Strang and Fix [26], the discretization error decreases in an L^2 -norm with $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ for \mathbb{P}_1 and with $\mathcal{O}(h^3)$ for \mathbb{P}_2 . This behavior is later used to argue about the dominant error term in the approximation.

2.3.2 Hybrid Tetrahedral Grids

All experiments within this thesis are conducted using the HPC FE framework HyTeG³ [7, 8].

By defining the weak formulation in eq. (2.24) on a grid Ω_h , it can be described as the LSE [26–28]. Since the size of these matrices increases quadratically with the problem size, the element matrix A for large problems usually does not fit the main memory of current supercomputers. To solve problems even at extreme scales, HyTeG uses matrix-free computations.

This is done by describing the computation steps of a problem as a kernel instead of assembling the element matrix. To facilitate the task of increasing the range of problems HyTeG can handle, a software library called HOG⁴ [9] is developed to automate the generation of such kernels. The classes of these kernels generated using HOG are called operator. In terms of HyTeG vocabulary, applying an operator is the matrix-free equivalent to applying the matrix-vector product $A\mathbf{v}$.

The problem size is the number of unknowns, also known as degrees of freedom (DoFs).

Computation of function norms HyTeG supports computations in the L^2 -space⁵, therefore allowing for approximating an integral by quadrature as described in section 2.2.2.

³Available at <https://i10git.cs.fau.de/hyteg/hyteg>

⁴Available at <https://i10git.cs.fau.de/hyteg/hog>

⁵Documentation regarding L^2 -spaces in HyTeG available at <https://hyteg.pages.i10git.cs.fau.de/hyteg/index.html>.

2.3.3 Multigrid Methods

HyTeG is specialized for the use of MG methods. It utilizes a hybrid grid hierarchy [7, 8, 10] with unstructured elements on the coarsest grid for flexible discretization of complex shaped domains, and uniformly structured elements on finer grids Ω_h to allow for performant matrix-free computations. Geometrically its FE are represented as tetrahedrals in 3D and as triangles in 2D. The unstructured coarse grid elements are called macro tetrahedrals.

The convergence rate per iteration for MG methods is independent of the grid refinement h , thus making them optimal solvers for large problem sizes. Therefore, a GMG method in the highest precision available (float64) is used as a reference solver for the ongoing discussion. In-depth information about MG is given, e.g., by Trottenberg et al. [30], Briggs et al. [29], and Hackbusch et al. [31].

2.4 Fixed precision approach

To get an idea of the accuracy impact of varying the precision for the fixed precision methods existing in the finite element framework HyTeG (section 2.3), a simple 2D Poisson Equation with RHS zero is solved in different precisions. The problem described in eq. (2.25) is discretized with two macro elements on a unit square, and solved on one of the student machines located at LSS using GMG as a solver.

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta \mathbf{u} &= 0 \\ \Omega &= [0, 1]^2 \\ \tilde{\mathbf{u}}|_{\Gamma_D} &= \mathbf{u} = \sin(x) \sinh(y)\end{aligned}\tag{2.25}$$

The two function spaces \mathbb{P}_1 and \mathbb{P}_2 are used for the discretization of Ω_h . To investigate the impact of precision, the entire solver is set to float32 once and to float64 the other time. Changing the precision of the framework is done at compile time by setting the compiler flag `WALBERLA_DOUBLE_ACCURACY` to either `ON` or `OFF`. Doing so sets the definition of the default datatype `real_t` to either float32 or float64. As can be seen from fig. 2.8b, for all runs, the residual is reduced until a plateau close to machine epsilon is reached. Since residual is within machine epsilon, the leading error term must either be the discretization error or the quantization error. With the same fixed precision method, discretization, and precision for the default `real_t` throughout a run, the error is affected only by the grid refinement h . To find the influence of varying precisions, the grid Ω_h is increasingly refined, and the error and the residual are computed in the \tilde{l}^2 norm for each level. From section 2.2.1 it is known that, if the problem is not affected by quantization error, the error should be reduced by the same amount as the discretization error; i.e., by a factor of $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$.

The approximated solution $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ is prolonged to the next finer grid before the error is computed to eliminate numerical artifacts. The absolute error in \tilde{l}^2 -norm is shown in

Figure 2.8: Error and Residual of Poisson Equation with zero RHS (eq. (2.25)) for \mathbb{P}_1 and \mathbb{P}_2 elements solved with fixed precision GMG at precisions. The target precision is changed by changing the value of `real_t`.

fig. 2.8a.

Figure 2.8a shows that the previous assumption holds. Up to a turning point, the error is reduced by $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ by increasing the refinement level. So, up to this point, the discretization error is the leading error. As described in section 2.2.1, when further refining the grid — past the turning point — the error increases again. This behavior is related to the quantization error. The turning point is where the quantization error surpasses the discretization error. The position of this point is related to the chosen precision and the order of discretization.

What becomes clear from this is that when using fixed precision methods, there are, in fact, limitations to accuracy. Once the accuracy of the solution is limited by the precision in which a problem is solved, the only way to further improve the solution is by increasing the number of bits used to represent a floating point number.

Figure 2.8 also shows, that even though refining the discretization past the turning point increases the error (fig. 2.8a), the residual converges towards machine epsilon nevertheless (fig. 2.8b). This Poisson Equation from eq. (2.25) is a textbook problem, and most practical problems cannot be solved analytically. For most problems, the error cannot be computed, and the residual is the primary information for estimating accuracy of the solution. This means that if no additional experiments are conducted, many numerically computed solutions might be incorrect. For some problems, higher-order discretization is necessary. In these cases, the issue of unnoticed quantization errors becomes even worse since the turning point shifts to coarser refinements for

higher order discretizations. With \mathbb{P}_2 elements in 2D, level 9 — i.e., around 1×10^6 DoFs — is the highest reasonable level of refinement when using float64. When reducing the precision to float32, after level 4 — i.e., around 1×10^3 DoFs — further increasing the resolution leads to a worse result.

Simply increasing the resolution does not guarantee improved accuracy. Without utilizing higher precisions, computational approximations cannot be improved after a certain point. Since utilizing high precision is costly and precisions higher than float64 usually not available, especially in the context of HPC, it is important to know when high precision is necessary and when not.

2.5 Mixed Precision

Unlike fixed precision, mixed precision utilizes various precisions at different solver parts to solve the same problem. Section 2.4 states that lower precisions are often not sufficient to solve a problem. However, utilizing a higher precision increases the memory transfer per iteration, thus increasing the runtime and energy consumption of a problem.

The idea behind mixed precision is to utilize high precision if necessary, but to reduce it whenever possible to improve performance.

2.5.1 Accuracy vs. Precision

According to Tamstorf et al. [4], the precision requirements vary for different sub-steps of an approximation method. For the description of a problem, the precision requirements increase more strongly with increased refinement, as it is the case for the precision requirements of the solver. They use IR to solve their model problem. This algorithm is also used as mixed precision solver and is described in section 2.5.2. In their paper, they state that the precision requirements increase in $\mathcal{O}(h^m)$ for the `innerSolver` (line 6 in listing 2.1) and in $\mathcal{O}(h^{k+m})$ for the computation of the residual (line 2 in listing 2.1). Where h is the refinement, k is the order of a FE discretization and $2m$ the order of the PDE. Thus, for a Poisson Equation with linear FEs (\mathbb{P}_1) discretization the requirement for the `innerSolver` increases with $\mathcal{O}(h^1)$ and for the residual with $\mathcal{O}(h^3)$; for a quadratic (\mathbb{P}_2) discretization they increase with $\mathcal{O}(h^1)$ $\mathcal{O}(h^4)$, respectively. From this, it can be seen that the precision requirements for the solver are much lower than for the representation of the problem, which in the case of IR is the residual. This becomes even more significant with increased discretization order of the problem.

Due to the dependency of k and precision requirement on the problem representation, the quantization error for the \mathbb{P}_2 discretization in fig. 2.8a becomes dominant faster than is the case for \mathbb{P}_2 . Another interesting observation from the results of Tamstorf

et al. is that with increased refinement the quantization error increases faster than the discretization error decreases; especially for low order PDEs. More information about the requirements to precision is given by Kohl et al. [6] and Tamstorf et al. [4].

Using IR, it is possible to decrease the precision of the solver — which is usually the costly part — as long as the residual is computed accurately enough.

2.5.2 Iterative Refinement

Using IR, the approximation ($\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$) is iteratively improved by solving the residual equation and using it in a correction scheme. Solving the residual equation is called `innerSolver`. The residual equation is depicted in eq. (2.26) and the formulation for the correction in eq. (2.27).

$$A\mathbf{e}_h = \mathbf{r}_h \quad (2.26)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}^{(i+1)} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}}^{(i)} - \mathbf{e}_h^{(i)} \quad (2.27)$$

Thus, IR is a correction scheme. Correction algorithms for iteratively solving a PDE have good numerical properties in terms of operational error [1, 24], since the magnitude of the correction parameter (\mathbf{e}_h) must not be the same as the magnitude of the solution \mathbf{u} .

This approach is very similar to the one of GMG except for the fact that IR generally operates only on one grid instead of a hierarchical grid structure, as GMG does. Furthermore, IR allows for an easy combination for different precisions. Henceforth, the precision in which the residual is computed is called the `bar-precision` ($\bar{\epsilon}$), and the precision for the `innerSolver` is called the `dot-precision` ($\dot{\epsilon}$). As suggested in section 2.5.1, for these precisions $\bar{\epsilon} > \dot{\epsilon}$ should hold, to produce correct results and benefit from low precision performance.

The algorithmic implementation of IR is presented in listing 2.1.

```

1 IR(dotA, barA, u, f):
2   r = f - barA u           // done in  $\bar{\epsilon}$  precision
3   r = round(r,  $\dot{\epsilon}$ )
4   initZero(e,  $\dot{\epsilon}$ )
5   loop i from 1 to N
6     solve(dotA r, e)      // done in  $\dot{\epsilon}$  precision
7   e = round(e,  $\bar{\epsilon}$ )
8   u = u - e

```

Listing 2.1: Schematic description of a IR algorithm. Line 6 is called the `innerSolve`.

It can be distributed in four core elements:

1. Computing the RHS of the residual equation; i.e., computing the residual (\mathbf{r}_h).
2. Iteratively solving the residual equation to get an estimate of the current error (\mathbf{e}_h).

3. Correcting the approximation ($\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$) by \mathbf{e}_h .
4. Casting the computed residual (\mathbf{r}_h) from $\bar{\epsilon}$ to ϵ , and casting the error estimate (\mathbf{e}_h) from ϵ to $\bar{\epsilon}$.

The iterative approximation to the residual equation of loop in lines 5–6 in listing 2.1 is called inner-solve. In addition to the chosen precisions, the number of inner-solve steps is a core parameter for fine-tuning the performance of IR as will be discussed in section 4.3.2.

By using GMG as an `innerSolver`, IR can utilize the benefits from MG methods. Therefore, for execution of the inner-solves GMG in low precision is chosen as `innerSolver`. The shorthands ϵ_{fp16} , ϵ_{fp32} , or ϵ_{fp64} are used to denote the precision the `innerSolver` is executed in. Using this vocabulary, applying a low precision matrix-vector product is called applying the operator `dotA`. In contrast, a high precision one is called applying the operator `barA`. These are the matrix-free equivalents of the element matrix A stored in ϵ , and $\bar{\epsilon}$, respectively.

2.5.3 Performance vs. Precision

Why utilizing low precisions can increase the runtime performance is demonstrated with the help of a simple roofline model [11].

Figure 2.9 depicts an exemplary roofline plot for a memory-bound problem. Reducing the data size that needs to be transferred per computation increases the arithmetic intensity. The number of FLOPS per computation is unaffected by its precision. Reducing the precision by half shifts the problem by a factor of two to the right; $I_{k_{\text{high}}} \rightarrow I_{k_{\text{low}}}$. The architecture bandwidth stays the same since the utilized precision does not affect it. Therefore, increasing the arithmetic intensity increases the attainable performance of a memory-bound problem.

Reducing the precision might change a memory-bound problem to a compute-bound one. This is depicted in fig. 2.9, where the low precision algorithm reaches the attainable peak performance and becomes compute-bound.

However, even if the code is compute-bound, reducing the precision might still increase the performance. Assuming that the given hardware supports vector acceleration — i.e., SIMD instructions — for the target precision, reducing the size per variable also increases the number of variables that can fit in a register. This increases the number of operations that can be executed in parallel per cycle, thus increasing the attainable peak performance of the code; $P_{\text{high}}^{\text{peak}_{\text{numa}}} \rightarrow P_{\text{low}}^{\text{peak}_{\text{NUMA}}}$.

Thus, reducing the precision by half can theoretically increase the performance up to a factor of two. Furthermore, since less memory is transferred, the energy consumption of the solver decreases independently of the runtime improvement.

Figure 2.9: Exemplary roofline model for a low and high precision algorithm. The compute-bound limit is denoted by the horizontal NUMA peak-performance lines. there are only two lines under the assumption that the target architecture support different NUMA instructions for the low precision ($P_{p_{low}}^{\text{peakNUMA}}$) and low precision ($P_{p_{high}}^{\text{peakNUMA}}$) floating point datatype. The dashed lines maps the arithmetic intensity of an algorithms to its attainable performance. For the low precision algorithm from $I_{k_{low}}$ to $P_{(p/k)_{low}}$, and for the high precision algorithm from $I_{k_{high}}$ to $P_{k_{high}}$. The value $P_{k_{low}}$ can be reached if the target architecture support NUMA instructions for the low precision datatype and therefore the compute-bound limit is increased from $P_{p_{low}}^{\text{peakNUMA}}$ to $P_{p_{high}}^{\text{peakNUMA}}$. Otherwise, the performance gets limited by the given computebound limit.

Implementing Mixed Precision in HyTeG

Applied precisions are float16, float32 and float64. The latter two are already supported by HyTeG to be used for fixed precision as demonstrated in section 2.4. Thus, part of this work is to enable computations using a mixture of various precisions, introducing a convenient workflow for it and extending supported precisions by float16. As mixed precision algorithm, IR according to Tamstorf et al. [4] is added as a new solver to HyTeG.

This chapter includes the use and modification of the frameworks HyTeG¹, HOG², waLBerla³, and pystencils⁴.

3.1 Prerequisites

HyTeG does not support mixed precision yet. Therefore, the requirements for HyTeG to make use of it are discussed within this section. Here, design choices, details about implementations, new features, and their test for correctness are outlined.

3.1.1 Mixed precision in General

Section 2.4 describes an approach to compare accuracy of PDE solves in different precisions. The way the problem is solved is not mixed precision, though. With mixed precision, one deals with a problem by handling different steps in the algorithm in different precisions, as described in section 2.5. The prerequisites for HyTeG necessary to handle the introduced problem are described in the following section.

¹HyteG at revision <https://i10git.cs.fau.de/hyteg/hyteg/-/tree/cc08fbfd057f25e576034b705455eb655f07a993>

²HOG at revision <https://i10git.cs.fau.de/terraneo/hyteg-form-generator/-/tree/5df6dbee6f366632bc5c20d91597172a653a37b3>

³waLBerla at revision <https://i10git.cs.fau.de/walberla/walberla/-/tree/b346f40576acef5c2521c7d7fc76b7d48735f1c0>

⁴pystencils at revision <https://i10git.cs.fau.de/terraneo/pystencils/-/tree/b77b93fc1788d246301a2e7f5d224d05b14cfd7f>

Casting Mixed precision means using datatypes of different precision within the same code. Function space classes in HyTeG are already type templated, so it is possible to use differently typed functions. Using them together, requires transforming data from one type to another; i.e., casting. Casting is implemented for \mathbb{P}_1 functions. It is done implicitly by copying the contents via the class method shown in listing 3.1.

```
1 targetFunction.copyFrom(sourceFunction, level);
```

Listing 3.1: Casting method between two functions of different datatype for one level.

Implicit casting may lead to unwanted compiler warnings, especially using float16. Thus, the `FunctionMemory` backend is changed from `std::vector::assign` — which relies on implicit casting — to an explicit cast before copying.

Mixed precision Algorithm Existing algorithms in hyteg make no use of mixed precision. Hence, IR is implemented according to section 2.5.2. An implementation draft can be found in listing 2.1. Since the residual equation (eq. (2.26)) is solved to correct the current approximation of $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$, additional temporary memory needs to be allocated. Both an additional residual-function \mathbf{r}_h and error-function \mathbf{e}_h must be available on the fine grid Ω_h in the lower precision ($\bar{\epsilon}$) and the high precision ($\acute{\epsilon}$). On all coarser grids down to the coarsest, both \mathbf{r}_h and \mathbf{e}_h must be available in $\acute{\epsilon}$ -precision as well. It is possible to pass the constructor a preallocated residual-function \mathbf{r}_h in $\bar{\epsilon}$ to save memory. All allocations for IR are done during the construction of the solver and freed by its destruction. For each call of the method `solve`, the following steps are executed in order:

1. The residual \mathbf{r}_h is computed in $\bar{\epsilon}$ -precision
2. The \mathbf{r}_h is cast from $\bar{\epsilon}$ -precision to $\acute{\epsilon}$ -precision
3. The eq. (2.26) is solved m -times in $\acute{\epsilon}$ -precision (m is defined during construction compare section 3.2)
4. The \mathbf{e}_h is cast from $\acute{\epsilon}$ -precision to $\bar{\epsilon}$ -precision
5. The approximation $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ is corrected in $\bar{\epsilon}$ -precision by \mathbf{e}_h according to eq. (2.27)

For the use case described in chapter 4, IR is thoroughly tested to ensure correct results are produced.

Operator Generation Solving PDEs in HyTeG requires forms. Implementations of forms exist already like the ones from the `FEniCS Project` [33]. They are hardcoded for float64 and therefore not applicable for mixed precision. However, the custom form generator, HOG from LSS can be adjusted to generate forms for data types. These forms are themselves used by a HyTeG object called operator. More complicated problems that cannot be solved by a constant stencil implementation can only be solved using a fixed precision approach or by assembling the global stiffness matrix. As

mentioned in section 2.3, one advantage of HyTeG is the use of performant matrix-free computations. Therefore, matrix-based solutions are not considered. Instead, this work aims to directly add to the current developments of generating high-performant operators with HOG [9].

HOG The existing generation of operators is extended by datatypes. A target floating point precision can be passed as an argument to HOG. This passed target precision is then converted to a framework-specific object called `HFGType`. An `HFGType` object consists of a `const qualifier` flag, an `identifier` that can handle general and encapsulated data types, and a representative `python-type` that is used by the backend. To not interfere with the current development of HOG, a `file-suffix` flag is added. If the suffix flag is set for an operator, a type describing is added to its filename. If not specified otherwise, the default HyTeG datatype `real_t` is used as target precision, and no suffix is added to the name of the generated file. Since the type `real_t` gives no information about the bit size of the target floating point-number, the type is assumed to be 64 bits long. Information about the bit length is essential to transform the AST for vectorization of kernels. The `HFGType` is designed as a type-interface to the backend `pystencils`, with the aspect of extensibility for arbitrary datatypes, including non-basic and software emulated ones in mind. The `HFGType` can be seen as an attribute of the operator. It is used only by the backend and, therefore, should not be modified during the generation of the AST. Before the kernels are printed, `pystencils` is called to add types to the kernel body.

The existing tests in HOG are extended to check the correct generation of `float16` and `float32` operators. These tests compare matrix-vector multiplications with generated operators and `Elementwise Operators` using `FEniCS Forms`. The test is accepted if the difference between the results for both kinds of operators is less than a precision specific threshold.

Pystencils To meet the needs for mixed precision in HyTeG, the generator backend `pystencils` is adjusted in the following ways. The `BasicType` is extended by an `identifier` that allows for non-generic type names. If no `identifier` is given, `pystencils` falls back to the default types chosen from a list according to the representative Python type used. The fact that the `identifier` is built on top of the original `BasicType` is also used to adjust the casting of numeric constants. Implicit casting during a multiplication upgrades the type to the largest multiplicand. So, to guarantee that computations are done in the target precision, implicit casting when multiplying with numerical constants must be avoided. If an `identifier` is specified, this is done by adding an explicit cast node in target precision around numeral nodes within multiplications in the AST. To account for non-basic and emulated floating point realizations the `pystencils` type-utilities function `collate_types` is adjusted to prefer non-basic types, so casting for nodes containing non-basic types prefers the non-basic type over the basic one. The information of the target precision is contained

only for the `lvalue` of the declaration. For the elements of the `rvalue` list of the declaration, no need for casting is detected. Therefore, the list would be printed in default precision, resulting in an unwanted `narrowing conversion` warning. To prevent this, if an `identifier` is specified, a direct cast around each element in the `rvalue` list of a `array declaration` nodes is printed.

Queries are added to the class `BasicType` to account for `float16` during transformation of the the AST and the `pystencils` algebra of is extended by `float16` keywords.

3.1.2 High Precision extension

Section 2.4 showed that not all problems can be solved using `float64`. To improve accuracy, nevertheless, the precision must be increased to datatypes larger than `float64`. In general, standard computing systems are not known to support floating point types past 64 bits. One reliable way to use reliable IEEE 754 conform datatypes larger than `float64` is to emulate floating point numbers.

One library that allows to emulate datatypes of arbitrary significand length is MPFR [32, 34]. As an experimental addition to the hardware supported floating point numbers, MPFR is introduced to HyTeG. Two interface libraries that allow MPFR to be used in a more C++ style are also included to ease usability. One of them, `mpfr::real` [35], defines the length of the significand at compile time. The datatype is templated and can be used like any ordinary C++ type. For the other one — i.e., `MPREAL` [36] — the significand length is defined at runtime. Both are added so the user can decide which way to use MPFR better fits their purpose.

By default, MPFR is not enabled. It can be done via the `cmake` option `HYTEG_BUILD_WITH_MPFR`. Tests whether MPFR is correctly installed, and for the general functionality and correctness are added to the HyTeG tests; i.e., `buildWithMPFRTest.cpp`, and `MPFRWrapperTest.cpp`, respectively

With described options, MPFR can be used as a datatype in HyTeG. To use MPFR with HyTeG's functions and operators, additional interface implementation is necessary. Some necessary steps for allowing to solve PDEs with MPFR are done within this work and outlined in section 3.1.1. The other steps, however, include fundamental changes in the backend of the code generator; i.e., `pystencils` [37]. Since a rework of `pystencils` is already ongoing, it makes little sense to focus on implementing a solution that will likely be discarded soon anyway.

Furthermore, here, MPFR is meant to be used to investigate problems where `float64` does not suffice to increase the accuracy further. As mentioned in section 2.4, this is the case for substantial problem sizes. MPFR types have no direct hardware acceleration, and additional overhead computations are necessary since the floating point numbers are only emulated [32]. Therefore, MPFR is extremely slow, using it for large problems is unrealistic, and for smaller problems, theory already exists [4–6].

Ultimately, the possible outcome of using MPFR for this master’s thesis is not promising enough to persuade further investigations of high precision computations. Instead, investigations are shifted to the other extreme, by focusing on improving performance of HyTeG using low precision datatypes for mixed precision.

3.1.3 Low Precision extension

Section 2.5 mentions, that using lower precision does not contradict accurate solutions [4–6]. To have a better understanding of the precision requirements and limitations to mixed precision in HyTeG, the framework is extended to support mixed precision for the three datatypes `float16`, `float32`, and `float64`; on \mathbb{P}_1 elements. The types `float32` and `float64` are already working for HyTeG, so this part of the thesis focuses on the inclusion of the lower precision floating point number `float16` into HyTeG as well as the challenges that come with it.

The type `_Float16` is chosen as a realization, as most other `float16` implementations are limited to GPUs or do not have a required standard in regards to their implementation on CPUs. On top of having inherently good performance on some modern CPU architectures, `_Float16` is IEEE 754 conforming. So, it can be used for performance-relevant codes and as well as error analysis.

Software Support For C++, `float16` is supported only since the CXX23 standard [38, 39]⁵. To support `float16` a compiler must include all features from the CXX standard paper P1467R9 [40]⁶.

Compiler Availability of these features is checked for the GNU [41] and the LLVM [42] C++ compilers. According to their websites, only version 13 of the GNU compiler `GCC13` includes all the necessities as of now. Tests are run to confirm the functionality of `float16` for the newest version of both compilers; i.e., `GCC13` and `CLANG17`. Only the newest version of the GNU compiler can compile `float16` codes without an error. This matches the information on `cppreference.com`⁷ which itself is recommended by the Standard C++ Foundation. Therefore, no further investigation of `float16` support for other compilers is done.

Cmake Since `float16` is fully supported only by the GNU compiler as of now, a compile option is added to separate the restricting `float16` codes from the rest of

⁵Since the CXX23 standard is not published yet, the current work-in-progress version is available at <https://github.com/cplusplus/draft>

⁶The contents from the paper “P1467R9 Extended floating-point types and standard names” are available at <https://www.open-std.org/jtc1/sc22/wg21/docs/papers/2022/p1467r9.html>

⁷Table of compiler compatibility for different CXX features is available at https://en.cppreference.com/w/cpp/compiler_support/23

the framework. To make sure that the rest of the codes can be compiled with other compilers, a pragma guard is added to all implementations related to float16 and all future implementations are expected to separate float16 implementations with this guard as well.

If the compile flag is activated, a simple cmake test is run to check if the current compiler supports features from float16. If the test produces an error, cmake terminates with a verbose error message.

Float16 in the framework According to the GNU manual [43] float16 for x86 architectures is represented by the C datatype `_Float16`⁸. For ease of usability and consistency with other floating point types, a type definition is added to the core module to use `_Float16` with the identifier `walberla::float16`.

Functionality and correctness of arithmetic computations using float16 combined with STL containers are added within the file `Float16SupportTest.cpp`.

MPI For inter-process communication on NUMA systems, MPI is used. In a discussion that started in 2017⁹, the MPI standard committee decided against including float16 support to the MPI standard¹⁰. Distributors of MPI are allowed to support float16. In general, MPI is incompatible with float16. To make sure that the implementation works independently of the installed MPI library, a custom MPI datatype, including associated MPI operations, is defined.

```
1 MPI_Datatype myMpiDatatype; // Declaring custom datatype
2 MPI_Type_contiguous(byteSize, MPI_BYTE, &myMpiDatatype); // Define custom
  type
3 // Allocation of custom MPI type
4 MPI_Op_create(&myMpiOperationDefinition, commutativeFlag, &
  myMpiOperationHandle);
5 MPI_Type_commit(&myMpiDatatype); // Register custom type
```

Listing 3.2: Allocation and definition of custom MPI types.

Adding support for custom datatypes for MPI requires the following things:

- Creating custom MPI datatype (listing 3.2).
- Creating a callback function of the custom MPI operation (listing 3.3). This must be done for all operations needed for each custom MPI datatype.
- Memory management of custom-defined datatypes and operations (listing 3.4).

⁸Half precision documentation for the GCC: <https://gcc.gnu.org/onlinedocs/gcc/Half-Precision.html>.

⁹Float16 discussion in the MPI forum available at <https://github.com/mpi-forum/mpi-issues/issues/65>.

¹⁰Result of the discussion from issue65 available at <https://github.com/mpi-forum/mpi-issues/issues/74>

When a custom MPI datatype and its associated operations are correctly defined and allocated, they can be used as every other datatype defined within the MPI standard, as shown in listing 3.5.

```

1 void myMpiOperationDefinition(void* rhs, void* lhs, int *len, MPI_Datatype
   *datatype) {
2 // Exemplary body:
3 // loop i from 1 to len
4 //     lhs[i] = lhs[i] OP rhs[i]
5 }
6
7 MPI_Op myMpiOperationHandle;
8 bool commutativeFlag = True; // Flag if cumulative conditions folds
9 \\ Allocation of custom MPI operator
10 MPI_Op_create(&myMpiOperationDefinition, commutativeFlag, &
   myMpiOperationHandle);

```

Listing 3.3: Allocation and definition of custom MPI operations.

```

1 MPI_Type_free(&myMpiDatatype);
2 MPI_Op_free(&myMpiOperationHandle1);
3 MPI_Op_free(&myMpiOperationHandle2);
4 // ....

```

Listing 3.4: Deallocation of custom defined MPI types and operations.

```

1 MPI_Reduce( &rhsValue, &lhsValue, count, myMpiDatatype,
   myMpiOperationHandle, recvRank, mpiCommunicator );

```

Listing 3.5: Exemplary usage of default MPI types.

Since manually handling the memory of user-defined MPI types for large software frameworks like HyTeG is barely manageable, Therefore, the `MPIManager` and `MPIWrapper` are adjusted to register user defined MPI types and operations. The `MPIWrapper` defines an `MPITrait` that connects a C++ type to an MPI type. The registration of user-defined MPI types and operations must be added to the MPI library An example of how this is done for float16 can be found within the file `MPIWrapper.cpp`. During the process of registration for custom types, the associated C++ type and its size in byte must be given to the `MPIManager`. There, the type is allocated, defined, and type specialized for its C++ within the `MPITrait` struct. The same holds for custom operations. Again, the user has to pass the C++ type associated with the operation, along with the name of the enum representing the operation and a pointer to the definition of the custom operation. The custom types and operations are allocated only if needed. The `MPIManager` keeps track of whether a type or an operation was called by the `MPITrait`. The data is allocated and stored within the manager's bookkeeping data structure during the first occurrence and returned to the user. For all other calls, the stored type or operation is simply returned. At the end of the program, the destructor of the `MPIManager` manager is responsible for freeing allocated types and operations, so the user does not have to worry about memory leaks. How custom-defined MPI types and operations are used by the user is shown in listing 3.6

```
1 MPI_Reduce( const_cast<T*>( &rhsValue ), &lhsValue, count, MPITrait<T>::  
    type(), MPITrait<T>::operation(operationName), recvRank,  
    mpiCommunicator );
```

Listing 3.6: Exemplary usage of `MPITrait` for user defined MPI types and operations.

In the current implementation, the definition of custom MPI types and operations must be added to the MPI library of the core module. This is done for `float16` and its operations `SUM`, `MIN`, `MAX`. Functionality and correctness for MPI `send`, `receive` and `reduce` with `float16` is added to the testsuite within the file `MPIFloat16Test.cpp`.

From this groundwork, a method could be developed that allows for registration and definition of new custom-defined MPI types and operations without interfering with the mpi library of the core module. Allowing definition and registration of custom-defined MPI types and operations would allow for general usage of MPI for other non-common datatypes, especially those too specific to include them to the core module. like, for example, various MPFR types with specific significand sizes that are probably used for one example only. However, to realize this change, the bookkeeping data structure embedded within the `MPIManager` must be adjusted to a smart data structure, that allows 1 – M relations between the N registered MPI types and it's associated M MPI operations per type. Since the mapping from an operation to an MPI operation happens via a C `enum`. In the current implementation, the resolution of operator names can only happen at runtime via `if` clauses. In my opinion, the easiest way to realize flexible bookkeeping is by changing the mapping of MPI operations to an `enum class`. This way, the mapping of MPI operations can easily be done via template arguments and does not need to be part of the core module. This, however, is an invasive change in HyTeG's backend that would affect large numbers of different files as well. Therefore, improving the registration of user-defined MPI types and operations is not followed further in this thesis.

HyTeG The optimized kernels for `add`, `apply`, `assign`, and `direct communication` only exist for `float64`, and `float32` at this point. For a reasonable comparison in terms of performance, for \mathbb{P}_1 functions, these kernels are extended by `float16`. For better maintainability and easy extension in the future, type templates are added for the kernels of these files instead of partially copying the code, to avoid duplication.¹¹

Functionality and correctness tests for \mathbb{P}_1 functions of `float16` type are added within the file `float16SupportTest.cpp` to HyTeG.

¹¹To add support for other spaces, code generation is recommended instead of by-hand coding since many kernels are needed that are all quite lengthy.

3.2 Interfaces

This section describes how to make use of the implemented mixed precision features in HyTeG and HOG. For detailed information about implementation, please refer to section 3.1.

To use mixed precision, the user is responsible for generating operators, allocating them and all functions in the right precision, when necessary, copy the values between functions of different precisions as described in listing 3.1. and use an appropriate solver; i.e., IR.

```

1 python3 ./generate_all_operators.py --quad-degree <degree-2D> <degree-3D> \
2                                     --hyteg <path> -p <fp-precision>
3                                     -f <form> -s <fct-space> \

```

Listing 3.7: Exemplary call to HOG with the optional precision argument “-p” and the necessary ones.

To distinguish operators with the same attributes but different target types, the `file-suffix` flag is set automatically if a target floating point precision is chosen. The floating point precisions currently known to the class `HFGType` are “-p fp16”, “-p fp32”, and “-p fp64” for float16, float32, and float64 respectively. The user can choose these three types, plus “-p real_t” for the default identifier `real_t`. Since `real_t` gives no information about the bit length of the datatype, using the default is discouraged.

```

1 typedef IterativeRefinementSolver< InnerOperator_t, ResidualOperator_t >
   Solver_t;
2 typedef GeometricMultigridSolver<InnerOperator_t> InnerSolver_t;
3
4 /// Initialization of the remaining objects.
5 /// In this case, the GMG solver is used as inner solver for IR.
6
7                                     :
8 // +++ Definition of IR-InnerSolver in ε +++
9 auto innerSolver = std::make_shared< InnerSolver_t >(
10     storage, smoother, coarseSolver, restriction, prolongation,
11     coarseLevel, maxLevel, preSmoothingSteps, postSmoothingSteps );
12
13 // +++ Definition of the IR-Solver in ε̄ +++
14 auto solver = std::make_shared< Solver_t >(
15     storage, dotA, innerSolver,
16     minLevel, maxLevel, numberOfInnerSolveCyclesPerIRSolve );

```

Listing 3.8: Exemplary initialization of the iterative refinement solver. `InnerOperator_t` is the type of the operator `dotA` in dot-precision used for solving the residual equation with the inner-solver. `ResidualOperator_t` is the type of the operator `barA` in bar-precision used to compute the residual which is passed during the call to the member function `solve`. The number of times the residual equation is iteratively solved with the `innerSolver` before the approximation is corrected and the function returns can be adjusted by `numberOfInnerSolveCyclesPerIRSolve`.

The generator generally works with all hardware-supported numeric types, including integers. The optimization “VECTORIZE” is supported for float32, and float64. If another identifier for supported types is needed, the `HFGType` can easily be extended.

For the IR algorithm described in section 3.1.1, two operators of possibly different precision must be used. One is used for the initialization and the other for the call to the method `solve`. In this example, operator `dotA` is allocated in ϵ precision and used for the initialization, while operator `barA` is allocated in $\bar{\epsilon}$ precision and used for the call to `solve`. Using IR only makes sense if $\bar{\epsilon} \leq \epsilon$ holds. The reason for this is mentioned in section 2.5. If $\bar{\epsilon} = \epsilon$, IR is used as a fixed precision solver.

The initialization process of the IR solver is shown in listing 3.8. The operator object `dotA` is passed during initialization of the solver object, it is used as `innerSolver` for the residual equation (line 6 of listing 2.1). Thus, the `innerSolver` object `innerSolver` and all objects used by it — e.g., `smoother`, `restriction`, etc. — must already be initialized in the same precision as `solver`; i.e., ϵ . Otherwise, the compilation returns with a type error.

```
1 solver->solve( barA, u, f, level );
```

Listing 3.9: *Exemplary call to the iterative refinement solver, with the operator `barA` in $\bar{\epsilon}$ -precision to compute the residual, the current approximation u , the RHS f and the grid level at which the problem is solved. The operator used for the `innerSolver` is passed and stored during initialization of the iterative refinement solver.*

The operator object of type `barA` is passed during the solver call, shown in listing 3.9. The object is used to compute the residual (line 2 of listing 2.1). The precision $\bar{\epsilon}$ in which the residual is computed, must match the precision of the approximated function object \tilde{u} and the right hand side function f .

Using `GeometricMultigridSolver` as a `innerSolver` for IR is not mandatory. All solvers compatible with operators generated by HOG can be used as `innerSolver`. The runtime performance of the IR solver depends on the number of inner-solve steps and the `innerSolver` used.

3.3 Hardware Support

Very few CPUs are capable use float16 without type conversion to float32 or float64 before computation and back to float16 after it. Instead, the compiler is making sure that float16 variables are stored in 16 bits and rounded to either float32 or float64 before the computation is performed. The result from that computation is then rounded back to float16 to be stored in a 16 bits variable. In theory, decreasing the transferred memory amount can still be helpful for memory-bound problems, as the arithmetic intensity of a code depends on the transferred memory not on the precision it is computed in (compare fig. 2.9). Objectively, the computations done in this “pseudo float16” manner can take even longer if too many casting operations are performed. Storing data in a different precision than the one for computations requires four instructions instead of one.

$$2 \times \text{ROUND UP} + 1 \times \text{OPERATION} + 1 \times \text{ROUND DOWN}$$

However, some CPU architectures that natively support float16 computations exist. One is the Sapphire Rapid architecture from Intel [23].

The hardware used for this thesis is discussed in the following. For development and testing purposes, one of the student computers¹² at LSS is used. Measurements for the discussion in chapter 4 are done on one of the Sapphire Rapid nodes¹³ from the Fritz computing cluster of NHR@FAU.

For a proper interpretation of the accuracy and performance output produced by the numerical experiment of section 4.3, it is essential to make sure that the computations done on the Platinum 8470 cores from the Sapphire Rapid generation directly use float16 instead of rounding before and after computations, the “stream-like” benchmark listing 3.11 is run for one core on both available machines. Benchmark metrics and event counters are measured with the performance tool LIKWID [44] from NHR@FAU. The executable is built with `-O3` optimizations and the tool is run as shown in listing 3.10 by pinning to thread 0 and choosing the `MEM_DP` performance group¹⁴.

```
1 likwid-perfctr -C 0 -g MEM_DP -m ./CheckFP16
```

Listing 3.10: *LIKWID execution*

Information to argue whether or not computations are actually done in float16 is gathered in table 3.1.

```
1 for (size_t i = 0; i < vsize; i++)
2   {
3     r[i] = v[i] + vv[i];
4   }
```

Listing 3.11: *stream-like triad benchmark*

The columns “instructions” and “CPI” from table 3.1 shows that the intel Platinum 8470 core actually uses computations with 16bits precision instead of rounding. For float32 and float64, the number of executed instructions is the same for the Xeon E3 and the Platinum 8470 cores, and the same holds for cycles per instruction. However, for the float16 benchmark on the Xeon E3 core, approximately four times as many instructions are executed in total and per cycle compared to the Platinum 8470 core. This observation perfectly matches the assumption that rounding is done before and after computations. The instructions are not increased for the run on the Platinum

¹²Everything is done on the machine `i10stud1`. Information about its Xeon E3 processor is available at <https://www.intel.de/content/www/de/de/products/sku/88177/intel-xeon-processor-e31275-v5-8m-cache-3-60-ghz/specifications.html>.

¹³Everything is done on nodes from the Slurm partition `spr1tb`. Detailed information about the machine’s specs can be found on the NHR@FAU website <https://doc.nhr.fau.de/clusters/fritz/>. Information about its Platinum 8470 processor is available at <https://www.intel.de/content/www/de/de/products/sku/231728/intel-xeon-platinum-8470-processor-105m-cache-2-00-ghz/specifications.html>.

¹⁴Since the version of LIKWID supporting float16 counters is not available on the Fritz computing cluster at the time of writing, a statement is produced from the available information instead of Packed HP counters.

CPU	Runtime (s)	Instructions	CPI	Energy (J)	Data (GB)
float16					
Xeon	0.1826	1.20×10^9	0.60	2.647	0.80
Plat	0.0407	3.75×10^7	4.06	7.894	0.79
float32					
Xeon	0.0620	7.50×10^7	2.96	0.824	1.60
Plat	0.0809	7.50×10^7	4.08	16.01	1.60
float64					
Xeon	0.1285	1.50×10^8	3.15	1.924	3.21
Plat	0.1619	1.50×10^8	4.08	31.72	3.21

Table 3.1: “Xeon” stands for a *Xeon E3* core and “Plat” for a *Platinum 8470* core. The clock frequency for all measurements is 3.8 GHz. For the Platruns frequency is pinned, but for the Xeonruns this was not possible, so the frequency varies ± 0.2 GHz. “Runtime” is the RDTSC^a runtime in seconds, “Instructions” is the number of instructions counted for the entire benchmark loop, “CPI” stands for cycles per instruction, “Energy” stands for consumed Energy in J, “Data” represents the data in GBytes that is totally transferred for the benchmark loop. ^aRDTSC is a machine instruction that halts the timer of the current process if another thread is scheduled during the runtime of this thread. Therefore, it represents the time work was done instead of the wall clock time.

8470 core since computations could be executed directly. The fact that the instruction count is not increased by exactly four times stems from the fact that the entire benchmark loop is counted, not only the computation itself.

Other interesting information can be obtained from table 3.1, as well. Independent of whether the computations are actually done in float16 or not, the transferred memory is halved from float32 to float16 and quartered from float64 to float16. No performance boundary is hit since the problem size of these benchmarks is way too small. Nevertheless, the runtime and the needed amount of energy could be reduced by a factor of two by reducing the precision by this factor, showing how beneficial the use of mixed precision can be.

This factor of two is the ideal outcome that can be achieved. chapter 4 focuses on the question of whether this performance gain can be achieved for solving a PDE with HyTeG using IR as a solver.

Numerical Experiment

This chapter focuses on the quality of the mixed precision implementation described in chapter 3. The discussion about quality can be split into two parts. The first part is about the general correctness of this method; i.e., “How applicable is it?”. This is done by comparing the error of a mixed precision application to a fixed precision GMG approach. The second one is the increase in performance using mixed precision in HyTeG, i.e., “How fast it has become?”. For this the runtimes between a accurate mixed precision setup and fixed precision GMG are compared.

Before results are discussed, the problem setup for this numerical experiment is given in section 4.1.

4.1 Benchmark Setups

This section describes how the investigations for the problem of chapter 4 are performed. It states the benchmark problem (section 4.1.1), the interface of the benchmark suite, including the solver structure (section 4.1.2), and the parameters (section 4.1.3) used for benchmarks discussed in chapter 4.

Two kinds of benchmarks are run. All runs aim to reduce the error close to discretization error, $\mathcal{O}(e_{\text{disc}})$. The first benchmark focuses on finding the accuracy limits for each configuration of precisions; i.e., for a given discretization how much can the solver precision be reduced, without losing accuracy. The results of these runs are discussed in section 4.2. The other benchmark run is meant to investigate the increase in performance that can be gained without losing accuracy. The results of these runs are discussed in section 4.3.

Both benchmarks are performed on the Fritz computing cluster using the `Platinum 8470` cores of the Sapphire Rapid generation. Details about the cluster system can be found in section 3.3. The accuracy limitation benchmarks with one core per macro tetrahedral on the macro grid; i.e., 24 cores. For the performance benchmarks, only a single `Platinum 8470` core is used to ensure that communication does not affect results.

4.1.1 Model Problem

Instead of computing the error in the precision of the solver — i.e., $\bar{\epsilon}$ — as it is done in section 2.4. The error after each solver iteration is computed in the highest precision available $\hat{\epsilon} \equiv \text{float64}$, to reduce the influence of quantization on the presented accuracy results. For the accuracybenchmark, the converged error in the function L^2 -norm $\|\mathbf{v}\|_{L^2}$. The error to determine the stopping criteria of the solver iteration is computed in $\|\mathbf{v}_h\|_{\tilde{l}_2}$ on Ω_h . No additional prolongation of the approximation $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ is done to compute the error on the grid $\Omega_{\frac{h}{2}}$, since the error computation of $\|\mathbf{v}\|_{L^2}$ is already good enough. From the accuracybenchmark, it is known that the approximation of \mathbf{u} is accurate enough. Therefore, for precision, no costly computation of $\|\mathbf{v}\|_{L^2}$ is performed since only the runtime is of interest.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f} &= \sin(2x) \sinh(y) \cosh(z) \\ \mathbf{u}|_{\Gamma_D} &= 0.5 \sin(2x) \sinh(y) \cosh(z) \\ \Omega &= [0, 1]^3 \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

4.1.2 Benchmark Interface

The code example in listing 4.1 describes how users can run a benchmark.

```

1 walberla.start();
2 mpi.start();
3 Setup_T config = { .opt1 = value1, .opt2 = value2, ... };
4
5 solveLSEWithOperatorFold< Setup_t, Solver_t,
6                           InnerSolver_t, Residual_t... >
7 (config);

```

Listing 4.1: Example of how to use the benchmark interface. *Setup_t* is the setup struct. *Solver_t* is an enum representing the solver. *InnerSolver_t* is a operator in $\hat{\epsilon}$ precision. *Residual_t...* is a list of operators in $\bar{\epsilon}$ precision. The instantiated setup object *config* is the only runtime parameter passed to the interface. All other information is passed via templates.

A unified benchmark suite is created for the benchmark runs discussed in chapter 4. The suite consists only of header files. The main runtime flow is defined in *solvePDEOpGen.hpp*. A struct called **Setup** is defined in the header *Setup.hpp* that stores all the runtime information. Furthermore, trait structures are defined to ease using solver and grid transformation objects. They can be found in the files *solvePDEOpGen.hpp* and *solvePDEOpGen.hpp* respectively. The hierarchy between the solvers is also described within these two header files. The hierarchical structure implemented for these solvers is described in fig. 4.1. The user can easily pass one of the solvers within this tree structure to the benchmark interface. However, nodes from the tree can only be passed as they are. The structure itself cannot be modified. The oval nodes in the tree represent the solvers and the grid transformation operators. The possible solvers

Figure 4.1: Representation of the Solver Structure.

*Parameters defined in table 4.6.

^aAre hardcoded parameters.^bRepresents the maximal number of inverse power iteration cycles to approximate the spectral radius of A .

and smoothers are defined in an enum class passed as a template argument to the benchmark interface.

Solver Structure The compile time parameters are described in section 4.1.2

As can be seen from listing 4.1, when using the benchmark suite, a MPI and waLBerla environment ¹ must be initialized. A problem-specific configuration object holding all runtime parameters for a benchmark must be initialized. The possible runtime parameters and their values for the chapter 4 can be found in section 4.1.3.

¹For information about general usage of HyTeG refer to the documentation at <https://hyteg.pages.i10git.cs.fau.de/hyteg/index.html>

level	#DoFs-2D- \mathbb{P}_1	#DoFs-3D- \mathbb{P}_1	#DoFs-2D- \mathbb{P}_2	#DoFs-3D- \mathbb{P}_2
0	0.90×10^1	1.40×10^1	2.50×10^1	6.30×10^1
1	2.50×10^1	6.30×10^1	8.10×10^1	3.65×10^2
2	8.10×10^1	3.65×10^2	2.89×10^2	2.45×10^3
3	2.89×10^2	2.45×10^3	1.08×10^3	1.79×10^4
4	1.08×10^3	1.79×10^4	4.22×10^3	1.37×10^5
5	4.22×10^3	1.37×10^5	1.66×10^4	1.07×10^6
6	1.66×10^4	1.07×10^6	6.60×10^4	8.48×10^6
7	6.60×10^4	8.48×10^6	2.63×10^5	6.75×10^7
8	2.63×10^5	6.75×10^7	1.05×10^6	5.38×10^8
9	1.05×10^6	5.38×10^8	4.19×10^6	
10	4.19×10^6	4.30×10^9	1.67×10^7	
11	1.67×10^7		6.71×10^7	
12	6.71×10^7		2.68×10^8	
13	2.68×10^8			
14	1.07×10^9			
15	4.29×10^9			

Table 4.1: *DoFs per level in 2D and 3D for one \mathbb{P}_1 - or \mathbb{P}_2 -function. The DoFs are counted with the meshes `quad_8el.msh`, and `cube_24el.msh` for 2D, and 3D, respectively.*

The first four template arguments are mandatory for the function `solveLSEWithOperatorFold`. Any additional number of operators \bar{A} can be passed to the interface as well. IR is the only mixed precision solver implemented in HyTeG. So `InnerSolver_t` (\dot{A}) and `Residual_t` (\dot{A}) operator of different precision can only be used with IR. If another solver — e.g., GMG — should be used, it is essential that $\dot{A} \equiv \bar{A}$. Only the operators generated by HOG are typed. Almost all other operators known to HyTeG only support float64 (compare section 3.1.1).

The amount of memory allocated per level is computed to determine what problem sizes fit into the main memory of the cluster node.

The consumed memory for a given solver is computed according to the function `MeM(solver)`

$$\text{MeM}(\text{solver}) = \sum_f \sum_{l=\min_{f_l}}^{\max_{f_l}} \text{DoF}[l] \cdot \text{sizeof}(\epsilon_f) \quad (4.2)$$

where ϵ_f is the precision of the function, “`sizeof(ϵ_f)`” returns the the size of one DoF in this precision, `DoF[l]` returns the number of DoFs for the given level l , \min_{f_l} , \max_{f_l} return the minimal and maximal level at which this function f is allocated, respectively, Ω_f is a set that contains all functions that are involved for the given solver. All information about the functions f within Ω_f can be found within table 4.2.

4.1.3 Parameters

The `Setup` class contains the following runtime parameter:

context	precision	#Functions	Lvl	
			coarse	fine
general	$\bar{\epsilon}$	3	x	x
error	$\hat{\epsilon}$	2	x	x
operator-R	$\bar{\epsilon}$	1		x
operator-I	$\hat{\epsilon}$	1	x	x
init-tmp	$\hat{\epsilon}$	2	x	x
error-tmp	$\hat{\epsilon}$	1		x
IR-R	$\bar{\epsilon}$	2	x	x
IR-I	$\hat{\epsilon}$	2	x	x
GMG	$\hat{\epsilon}$	1	x	x
CG	$\hat{\epsilon}$	4	x	
Chebyshev smoother	$\hat{\epsilon}$	2	x	x

Table 4.2: Allocated functions for the benchmark setup, their precision and on which levels they are allocated.

solver	maxLvl	Memory Allocated
3D		
$IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}}_{fp32}$	9	0.85590 TB
$IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}}_{fp16}$	9	0.75986 TB
$GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}}_{fp64}$	9	0.93470 TB
$GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}}_{fp32}$	9	0.79927 TB
$GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}}_{fp16}$	9	0.73155 TB
2D		
$IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}}_{fp32}$	13	0.30928 TB
$IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}}_{fp16}$	13	0.25486 TB
$GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}}_{fp64}$	13	0.35510 TB
$GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}}_{fp32}$	13	0.27777 TB
$GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \hat{\epsilon} - \hat{\epsilon}}_{fp16}$	13	0.23911 TB

Table 4.3: Memory allocation estimate for solvers of interest for described problem setup and \mathbb{P}_1 discretization, the max levels at which they can be allocated on the Fritz computing cluster and a memory allocation assumption bast on described setup.

Parameter Name	accuracy and precision
Problem	“Poisson”
Dimension	3D
Mesh File	“cube_24el.msh”
Exact Solution	$0.5 \sin(2x) \sinh(y) \cosh(z)$
Right-Hand Side	$\sin(2x) \sinh(y) \cosh(z)$

Table 4.4: **Problem Parameters:** Description of the problem given to the benchmark file. More information about the problem is given in section 4.1.1 The first column gives the name of the problems property and the other ones the properties used for each run. The runs are, “accuracy” for the accuracy limitation benchmark in section 4.2, and “precision” for the performance benchmark in section 4.3.

Table 4.4 describes the problem that is solved for each benchmark. Table 4.5 describes the runtime controls of each benchmark. Table 4.6 describes the configurations used for the solvers that are represented in fig. 4.1.

CG is exclusively executed on grid level $l = 1$, after the first three iterations, the residual on the coarse-grid is already smaller than the discretization error on level 1 (compare table 4.10). Thus, it is concluded that five CG iterations on the course grid are sufficient.

Operators Used Since no vectorization for float16 is available yet, all accuracy-benchmarks discussed in section 4.2 are done with non-vectorized operators. To have a meaningful performance comparison, the precisionbenchmarks for section 4.3 use vectorized operators.

Solvers Used For GMG, and IR results shown in chapter 4, the **GMG Solver**, or **IR Solver** node represented fig. 4.1 are used respectively, with operators machining the required precision for each run.

4.2 Accuracy limitation benchmark

Before the general correctness of this mixed precision approach can be discussed, the term “correct solution” needs to be defined in the context of this thesis. Using numerical methods, a solution is barely ever 100% correct. However, the error can be reduced enough to accept an approximation as correct. Here, an approximation is accepted as correct if its error is in the order of the discretization error. To determine the discretization error the same problem is solved as accurately as possible. Once all other error sources are reduced, the final error per level is assumed to be the discretization error. The reference solution is configured as follows:

- As reference solver, GMG in float64 is chosen as it is the solver with the highest precision available.

Parameter Name	accuracy	precision
Level Range ^a	1–9 ^j	6–8 ^j
Stopping Criteria ^b	IT RR ER	IT ET
Max Iterations ^c	100	100
Max Residual Rate ^d	0.91	—
Residual Threshold ^e	—	—
Max Error Rate ^f	0.99	—
Error Threshold ^g	—	1.5 e_{disc} ⁱ
Residual Norm ^h	$\frac{\ \mathbf{v}_h\ _{\tilde{l}^2}}{\ \mathbf{v}_{h,\text{ref}}\ _{\tilde{l}^2}}$	$\frac{\ \mathbf{v}_h\ _{\tilde{l}^2}}{\ \mathbf{v}_{h,\text{ref}}\ _{\tilde{l}^2}}$
Error Norm ^h	$\ \mathbf{v}_h\ _{\tilde{l}^2}$	$\ \mathbf{v}_h\ _{\tilde{l}^2}$

Table 4.5: **Runtime Control Parameters: Description of possible runtime Parameters:**

^aThe refinement levels for which this benchmark run is executed.

^bChosen condition for stopping the iterative approximation to solution. Possible conditions are “...”: **Stop if** ...

“IT”: ^cThe maximal number of iterations is reached.

“RR”: ^dThe residual converged; i.e., residual rate > “Max Residual Rate”.

“RT”: ^eThe residual is small enough; i.e., residual norm < “Residual Threshold”.

“ER”: ^fThe error converged; i.e., error rate > “Max Error Rate”.

“ET”: ^gThe error is small enough; i.e., error norm < “Error Threshold”.

^hNorm used for comparison with the threshold; i.e., “RT” or “ET”.

ⁱThe values used for the discretization error (e_{disc}) per level are defined in table 4.10.

Definition of the runtime configurations for each benchmark. The value “—” means that this configuration is not used for the related benchmark. The first column gives the name of the runtime configuration and the following ones the values used for each run. The runs are,

“accuracy” for the accuracy limitation benchmark in section 4.2, and

“precision” for the performance benchmark in section 4.3.

(^jUsing float16 as smoother precision ϵ , the problem for benchmark accuracy is refined only to level 4. Refining the problem further creates zeros on the diagonal of \hat{A} , resulting in **division by zero** runtime errors. For the benchmark precision, float16 is not used at all. The reason for that can be found in section 4.2.2.)

Parameter Name	accuracy	precision
IR Smooths ^a	1	1, 4
Pre Smooths ^b	1	1
Post Smooths ^c	1	1
Chebyshev Order ^d	1	1
Coarse Level ^e	1	1
Threshold ^f	$10 \times \min_{x \in \hat{\epsilon}} \hat{x} $	$10 \times \min_{x \in \hat{\epsilon}} \hat{x} $
CG Iterations ^g	5	5

Table 4.6: **Solver Parameters: Description of possible solver Parameters:**

^aNumber of times the residual equation in the IR solver is smoothed before the residual is recomputed.

^bNumber of pre smooths for the MG solver.

^cNumber of post smooths for the MG solver.

^dPolynomial order of the Chebyshev smoother.

^eThe refinement level at which the coarse grid Ω_{2h} is solved.

^fCoarse Grid solve stops earlier, if the absolute residual norm $\|\mathbf{v}_h\|_{\hat{\epsilon}}^2$ is smaller this number.

^gMaximal number of iteration from the CG solver that are performed on the coarse grid Ω_{2h} . Parameter studies showed that throughout all configurations this is the optimal number.

Configurations for the solver and smoother defined in section 4.1.2 and fig. 4.1. The first column gives the name of the solver configuration and the following ones the values used for each run. The runs are,

“accuracy” for the accuracy limitation benchmark in section 4.2, and

“precision” for the performance benchmark in section 4.3.

Pragma Name	accuracy	precision
PERFORMANCE_RUN ^a	OFF	ON
DEACTIVATE_FLOATING_CHECKS ^{b,g}	OFF	ON
WRITE_BENCHMARK ^c	ON	ON
USE_WEAK_NORM ^d	ON	OFF
WRITE_VTK ^e	OFF	OFF
CHECK_FOR_UNDERFLOW ^f	OFF	OFF

Table 4.7: **Preprocessor Parameters: Description of Pragma macros:**

^aMinimizes verbos output and force changes some of the other Pragas to reduce generation of output files and float checks.

^bSuppression of runtime float checks.

^cGeneration of summary file.

^dComputation of (costly) weak L^2 norm. By default, all norms are computed and printed to the summary file.

^eGeneration of VTK output.

^fEnabling underflow checks.

Setting of the preprocessor macros known to the benchmark suite for all benchmark runs. The first coulumn gives the name of the preprocessor macro and the following ones the values used for each run. The runs are,

“accuracy” for the accuracy limitation benchmark in section 4.2, and

“precision” for the performance benchmark in section 4.3.

(^gUsing float16 as smoother precision ϵ , DEACTIVATE_FLOATING_CHECKS are always disabled. The coarse grid solver is set to stop after 5 iterations or when the absolute residual norm falls below the machine precison of `real_t`. Since the smallest number of float16 is already larger than ϵ , a flush to zero for the residual norm is likely to happen, causing **division by zero** errors during CG solve.)

- The solver is iteratively applied until convergence of the residual.
- The residual is reduced to the order of machine epsilon.
- It is checked whether the remaining error in the L^2 -norm decreases with increased refinement as expected of the discretization error; i.e., with $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$.

4.2.1 Comparison of different solvers in terms of accuracy

This chapter investigates whether the reference solver suffices given correctness criteria. The other solvers of interest are included in the discussion to determine differences between them, and the reference one is this process.

To demonstrate that the influence of the remaining residual on the quality of the approximation is only minor, the final relative residual (a) in \tilde{l}^2 -norm, the relative total error (b) in L^2 -norm, and the number of solver iterations (c) to achieve target accuracy are respectively presented for each refinement level within fig. 4.2.

This figure contains the information of two different benchmark runs. One in which the solution to the Poisson Equation is iteratively approximated until the residual converges (I). For the other run, the approximation terminates if either total error or residual converge (II).

Figure 4.2-Ia shows, that after only three refinement steps, the error for all the float16 solvers increases again with increased refinement. For the fixed precision float32, the error decreases in accordance with the reference solver until level 7. After that, the error increases again, as is the case for all the float16 solvers. The error of the IR solver utilizing a float32 `innerSolver` (ϵ_{f32}), however, decreases in the same manner as it is the case for the reference one for all levels that could be investigated in the given main memory limitations. Thus, according to the theory of Tamstorf et al. [4], using IR significantly improves the range for which float32 can be applied as precision for the `innerSolver`.

The graph of the reference solver, as well as the one from IR with float32 `innerSolver`, have a linear slope in the logarithmic scaling, proving the exponential reduction of discretization error for increased refinement. A check of whether both of them decrease in $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ is done in the next section of this discussion.

Figure 4.2-Ib illustrates that for all configurations — except the float16 ones — the residual can be reduced to the order of the machine epsilon (ϵ_M) in which the residual for IR is computed ($\bar{\epsilon}$); for GMG it the order of ϵ_M in the precision in which the problem is solved ($\bar{\epsilon}$).

Even at the levels where the error of the low precision solvers is still in the order of the reference one, the residual is still always reduced to the order of machine epsilon.

Another benchmark run is performed (II). For this one the approximation stops if either the error, or the residual converge. this is symbolized by $\mu_{\|e\|} \rightarrow 1$, or $\mu_{\|r_h\|} \rightarrow 1$,

Figure 4.2: This figure shows row-wise the relative error in the L^2 -norm (a), the relative residual in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm (b), and the total number of solver iterations (c), per level. Column-wise stopping criterion for the run is given, (I) terminates when the residual rate converges ($\mu_{\|r_h\|} \rightarrow 1$), and (II) once either the residual or the error in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm ($\mu_{\|r_h\|} \rightarrow 1 \vee \mu_{\|e\|} \rightarrow 1$) converges. It contains $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \epsilon}$ runs for ϵ_{fp16} , and ϵ_{fp32} , as well as $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \epsilon}$ runs for ϵ_{fp16} , ϵ_{fp32} , and ϵ_{fp64} . Float16 runs are presented only up to level 4. These methods are not stable for higher levels, and runtime errors occur. Figure 4.2 also misses some datapoints for GMG in ϵ_{fp16} . During the simulation, these values were flushed to zero due to float underflow, so they can not be represented in this logarithmic scaling of this figure. The dashed horizontal line represents the rounding machine precision ϵ_M for the floating point type that starts next to it. The expected convergence rate in big-O notation is given as diagonal dotted line with the relative error in the L^2 -norm of $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \epsilon}$ on level 1 as line origin. The dashed horizontal line represents the rounding machine precision ϵ_M for the floating point type that starts next to it.

respectively. Changing the stopping criterion does not affect the error ($Ia \rightarrow IIa$) visibly.

However, the effort needed to approximate the solution changes drastically. Comparing Ic and IIc presents that for some configurations, the number of solver iterations decreases by more than a factor of 2. The difference in executed iterations is explained by comparing Ib and IIb . Especially for a high `residual compute` precisions method, the residual is not even close to convergence when the total error is, resulting in many superfluous iterations.

Summarizing the insights gained from Figure 4.2 shows that GMG in float64 suffices as a reference solver and that the solution approach can be stopped before convergence of the residual without compromising accuracy.

Figure 4.2-IIc shows that using the stopping criteria of column II, all solver configurations need almost the same number of iterations to reach almost the same approximation quality. Thus, the problem is not “over-solved”, allowing for a fairer comparison between approaches. For the performance investigations of section 4.3, having a fixed “quality” target as a stopping criterion for all methods to describe which solver reaches a certain accuracy the fastest is even better.

4.2.2 Result of float16 mixed precision

For measurements of float16 approaches, hardly any statement could be identified. Therefore, this section focuses on the results of these solvers in particular.

For the discussion of the general usability of a float16 application, a IR solver run with float16 `innerSolver` precision and float64 `residual compute` precision ($IR_{\epsilon \gg \dot{\epsilon}_{fp16}}$) is added to the measurement results.

Closer look at the converged results

As can be seen from fig. 4.3 I, there is no benefit to using an even higher `residual compute` precision for the $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp16}$ IR solver. If anything, the results become worse for these computations (Ia level 4).

When changing the stopping criterion — as discussed in section 4.2.1 — the error of this particular point improves to be in the order of $IR_{\epsilon > \dot{\epsilon}}$. This leads to the assumption that the residual equation for $IR_{\epsilon \gg \dot{\epsilon}}$ in figure Ia is over-solved. Comparing the residual measurements (b) for this setup, no difference can be found in this regard, though.

At level 2, the residual increases for the IR solvers by changing the stopping criterion ($Ib \rightarrow IIb$). Thus raising the question of whether the linear system $A_h \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h = \mathbf{f}_h$ for a resolution higher than level 2 is insufficiently solved using $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp16}$.

Since no visual benefit is identified when increasing the precision in which the residual is computed, no further investigations regarding $IR_{\epsilon \gg \dot{\epsilon}}$ are done.

Figure 4.3: This figure shows row-wise the relative error in the L^2 -norm (a), and the relative residual in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm (b), per level. Column-wise stopping criterion for the run is given, (I) terminates when the residual rate converges ($\mu_{\|r_h\|} \rightarrow 1$), and (II) once either the residual or the error in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm ($\mu_{\|r_h\|} \rightarrow 1 \vee \mu_{\|e\|} \rightarrow 1$) converges. It contains $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \dot{\epsilon}}$, $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} \gg \dot{\epsilon}}$, and $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}}$ runs for $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp16}$. The $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} \gg \dot{\epsilon}}$ runs are iterative refinement runs with float16 innerSolver precision and float64 residual compute precision (instead of float32). The dashed horizontal line represents the rounding machine precision ϵ_M for the floating point type that starts next to it. The expected convergence rate in big-O notation is given as diagonal dotted line with the relative error in the L^2 -norm of $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}} - \dot{\epsilon}_{fp64}$ on level 1 as line origin. The dashed horizontal line(s) with (I) (II) next to it show the point in the respective quantity where the approximation starts to diverge for the stopping criteria (I) or (II).

Convergence behavior of Error and Residual for float16

To gain a better understanding of how error and residual change with every iterative application of IR, the discrete l^2 -norm for both quantities is given in fig. 4.4. The setup for this figure is the one where the problem is approximated until convergence of the residual ($\mu_{\|r_h\|} \rightarrow 1$). Both quantities are given in the discrete norm relative to their initial values after initialization, error in (a) and residual in (b). Measurements related to $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \bar{\epsilon}_{float16}}$ are denoted with orange stars, while for comparison, the ones of $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \bar{\epsilon}_{float16}}$ are given as green circles as well. The respective levels are indicated by a color bar with lighter colors representing the coarser maximal refinement levels and darker colors the finer ones.

Figure 4.4 a illustrates that for all levels, there is no difference in error convergence rate between both solver approaches. However, using IR allows additional solver iterations compared to GMG throughout the levels. For levels 2 and 3, the error is already at the point of convergence, whereas for level 4, the error is still reducing at the same rate. Thus, using float16 IR results in a better accuracy compared to float16 GMG. The improvement is very minimal, though, and it is not possible to extend the refinement range for which float16 can be applied, as is the case for IR using float32.

Comparing part b of this figure shows that utilizing IR generally produces a lower residual. Furthermore, both solvers reach residual convergence even at level 4.

These results show that it is very likely that the float16 solver is still stable at level 4 but that the problem in the solver needs to be represented more accurately. Moreover, the float16 solver produces floating point errors that cause the program to terminate instead of increasing the error; as is the case for the float32 solver. This floating point error is likely the result of a division where the divisor is flushed to zero. Reformulating this division [1, 24] or increasing the precision for this computation will likely result in the applicability of a more comprehensive refinement range for the float16 solver.

Another general idea to improve named range is to split the `innerSolver` further and extend the correction method used in GMG to a hierarchical IR like approach where the fine grid residual is computed in float64, the general `innerSolver` in float32 and only some computations — e.g., the matvec — are performed on float16.

4.2.3 Quantification for performance stopping criteria

This subsection focuses on finding a common target error as a stopping criterion to have a fair performance comparison that does not compromise accuracy.

According to section 2.5.1, the error measured in L^2 -norm of a Poisson Equation — which is used as a model problem for this chapter — is expected to decrease in $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ for a linear (\mathbb{P}_1) discretization.

To determine whether the error improves in named order, its slope is referenced in

Figure 4.4: This figure shows row-wise the relative error in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm (a), and the relative residual in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm (b), per iteration. The stopping criterion for this run convergence of the residual rate ($\mu_{\|r_h\|} \rightarrow 1$). It contains $IR_{\bar{\epsilon}>\hat{\epsilon}}$ (orange), and $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\hat{\epsilon}}$ (green) runs for $\hat{\epsilon}_{fp16}$. It is graph is given for level 2 to 4. The higher the level, the darker the color. The dashed horizontal line represents the rounding machine precision ϵ_M for the floating point type that starts next to it.

Precision		Solver	Level									
Residual	InnerSolver		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
16	16	GMG	E	E	R	R	NaN					
32	16	IR	E	E	R	R	NaN					
32	32	GMG	E	E	E	E	E	R	R	R	E	
64	32	IR	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	E
64	64	GMG	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	E	E

Table 4.8: Shows which simulation configurations terminated at each level for which criteria. Termination due to error convergence is represented as “E”, Termination due to convergence of residual is represented as “R”, Termination due to the number of max iterations reached is represented as “I”, and if the simulation diverged, it is represented as “NaN”.

fig. 4.5. There the relative error, computed in the L^2 -norm $\frac{\|e\|_{L^2}}{\|e_{\text{ref}}\|_{L^2}}$ is plotted for all investigated solver configurations.

For the ϵ_{fp16} solvers the error reduces with $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ only to level 3. For higher refinements, the error diverges. The point of the least accurate solution is highlighted with a green arrow. At this point, the relative error is approximately 6.9 times the machine epsilon of float16. Deeper examination of mixed precision using float16 is done in section 4.2.2.

For ϵ_{fp32} , the ideal reduction in error with increasing resolution continues up to level 7. So using $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\epsilon}$ with float16 past level 6 might misrepresent the capable performance since it is likely that too many iterations are needed to reach the target quality. This point is again highlighted, this time marked with an orange arrow. Here, the relative error is approximately 200 times the machine epsilon of float32.

Here, the advantage of mixed precision takes effect. By using a more precise computation of the residual — i.e., a more accurate representation of the problem — ϵ_{fp32} can be utilized for better-refined problems. In the case of fig. 4.5, $IR_{\bar{\epsilon}>\epsilon-\epsilon_{fp32}}$ is as accurate as solving the problem in float64 precision. Assuming that a solver iteration is faster when utilizing a lower precision, this also means that for this setup, pure $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\epsilon-\epsilon_{fp32}}$ would be the best solver to choose up to level 6, since, according to fig. 4.2-IIc, all solvers take the same amount of iterations to converge.

Defining the target Quality

Table 4.8 shows which stopping criteria are met for each benchmark run. The shortcuts I, R, and E symbolize termination due to “exceeded maximal number of iterations”, “convergence of the residual rate”, or “convergence of the error rate”, respectively.

From table 4.8, it can be seen that for most runs, the error converges faster than the residual, as observed in section 4.2.1. However, contrary to the review of fig. 4.2 in the last section, the residual for $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\epsilon-\epsilon_{fp32}}$ converges faster than the total error, even for level 6. This might have two reasons, one of which is that the stricter requirement on

Figure 4.5: This figure shows the relative error in the L^2 -norm, per level. The approximation stops when either the residual rate or the error rate converge in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm ($\mu_{||r_h||} \rightarrow 1 \vee \mu_{||e||} \rightarrow 1$) It contains $IR_{\bar{\epsilon}>\epsilon}$ runs for $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp16}$, and $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32}$, as well as $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\epsilon}$ runs for $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp16}$, $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32}$, and $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp64}$. Float16 runs are presented only up to level 4. These methods are not stable for higher levels, and runtime errors occur. Figure 4.2 also misses some datapoints for GMG in $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp16}$. During the simulation, these values were flushed to zero due to float underflow, so they can not be represented in this logarithmic scaling of this figure. The levels where the approximation starts to diverge are highlighted by arrows in the color of the respective precision. The dashed horizontal line represents the rounding machine precision ϵ_M for the floating point type that starts next to it. The expected convergence rate in big-O notation is given as diagonal dotted line with the relative error in the L^2 -norm of $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\epsilon}$ on level 1 as line origin.

level	$GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp16}}$	$IR_{\bar{\epsilon}>\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp16}}$	$GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32}}$	$IR_{\bar{\epsilon}>\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32}}$	$GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp64}}$
1	9.02×10^{-4}	1.38×10^{-3}	3.42×10^{-3}	2.14×10^{-3}	2.08×10^{-3}
2	6.47×10^{-3}	7.05×10^{-3}	7.70×10^{-3}	8.13×10^{-3}	6.97×10^{-3}
3	8.99×10^{-3}	1.17×10^{-2}	1.47×10^{-2}	1.70×10^{-2}	1.53×10^{-2}
4	8.85×10^{-3}	1.23×10^{-2}	2.73×10^{-2}	3.08×10^{-2}	2.78×10^{-2}
5			6.42×10^{-2}	7.64×10^{-2}	6.81×10^{-2}
6			2.65×10^{-1}	3.36×10^{-1}	2.78×10^{-1}
7			1.73	2.52	2.05
8			1.18×10^1	2.15×10^1	1.76×10^1
9			8.12×10^1	1.86×10^2	1.50×10^2

Table 4.9: Time to solution in s for the accuracy benchmark run with stopping criteria $\mu_{\|e\|} \rightarrow 1 \vee \mu_{\|r_h\|} \rightarrow 1$.

$\mu_{\|e\|}$ compared to $\mu_{\|r_h\|}$ — as stated in table 4.5 — is more influential than anticipated. The other is that since absolute norm values of error and residual are used as stopping criteria, the magnitude of the residual is way higher compared to the one of the error, resulting in a less noticeable change in error compared to the change of the residual. Nevertheless, since the stopping criterion used for the performance benchmarks is purely error-based, it is likely that the fixed precision GMG in float32 will not converge at all, even for 6.

Since runtime is used as performance metric, the runtimes per level for all investigated solver setups are compared to determine at which level the runtimes are high enough to produce a reasonable performance comparison without overestimating the influence of noise. Table 4.9 contains the time-to-solution for the $\mu_{\|e\|} \rightarrow 1 \vee \mu_{\|r_h\|} \rightarrow 1$ runs.

It can be seen that the low-resolution runs are too short to investigate performance quantitatively. All approximations with a resolution below level 7 take less than a second to compute. For those runs, the influence of noise might be too significant, making them unreliable candidates to argue about performance benefits correctly. All available benchmark configurations using $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp16}$ are too short, so they are not considered for the performance discussion.

For the sake of average runtime comparison between the fixed precision solvers in different precision, GMG float32 is included in the performance discussion, even though no reliable results for high resolutions are expected. Since level 6 included the last possibly accurate result from this solver configuration, the performance argumentation is chosen to include the levels 6 to 9.

The configurations of interest are, therefore, GMG with float32 ($GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32}}$), GMG with float64 ($GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp64}}$), and IR with a **residual compute** precision ($\bar{\epsilon}$) of float64 and **innerSolver** precision ($\dot{\epsilon}$) of float32 ($IR_{\bar{\epsilon}>\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32}}$) at level 6 – 9.

To reach an adequate solution without risking to reach the area where the error is barely reduced per iteration, the threshold is set to a factor C times the discretization error in the discrete l^2 -norm.

level	$\ \tilde{u}_h - u_h\ _{\tilde{l}^2}$	$\ \tilde{u}_h - u_h\ _{\infty}$	$\ \tilde{u}_h - u\ _{L^2}$	$\frac{\ \tilde{u}_h - u\ _{L^2}}{\ u\ _{L^2}}$
1	9.53×10^{-3}	1.78×10^{-2}	1.20×10^{-2}	4.13×10^{-2}
2	1.95×10^{-3}	6.54×10^{-3}	3.29×10^{-3}	1.13×10^{-2}
3	4.36×10^{-4}	2.24×10^{-3}	8.62×10^{-4}	2.96×10^{-3}
4	1.03×10^{-4}	7.15×10^{-4}	2.20×10^{-4}	7.54×10^{-4}
5	2.51×10^{-5}	2.17×10^{-4}	5.53×10^{-5}	1.90×10^{-4}
6	6.21×10^{-6}	6.41×10^{-5}	1.39×10^{-5}	4.75×10^{-5}
7	1.54×10^{-6}	1.85×10^{-5}	3.46×10^{-6}	1.19×10^{-5}
8	3.84×10^{-7}	5.27×10^{-6}	8.66×10^{-7}	2.97×10^{-6}
9	9.59×10^{-8}	1.48×10^{-6}	2.17×10^{-7}	7.43×10^{-7}

Table 4.10: Error of the GMG solver in float64 for different error norms.

The errors of the $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{ff64}}$ benchmarks after convergence are used as reference discretization error, since float64 is assumed to produce the most accurate result. The converged error in different norms can be found in table 4.10. As is stated in table 4.5 of section 4.1.3 as well, $C = 1.5$ is chosen as the factor.

To be absolutely sure that the new stopping criteria $\|e\|_{\tilde{l}^2} < C\|e_{\text{disc}}\|_{\tilde{l}^2}$ produces results with a quality in the same order as the one before, the differences between both runtime configurations are illustrated in fig. 4.6. With the column I representing the previous runtime setup and II the new setup with a fixed error threshold as quality target. As for the previous plots, the rows represent error (a), residual (b), both in \tilde{l}^2 -norm and solver iterations (c).

Note that this time, plots in this figure are represented in the \tilde{l}^2 -norm. This is not an optimal norm to compute the error in, since phenomena like superconvergence [27, Chapter 4.9.3] could slightly be distorted. Since $\|v_h\|_{\tilde{l}^2}$ is used within the termination criterion, the figure is given in this norm regardless.

Due to the chosen norm, the points in fig. 4.6-a lie below the optimal reference line. The order in which the error is reduced is still in $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$. Most importantly, the relevant configurations all have the same illustrated properties. The relevant configurations are: $IR_{\bar{\epsilon}>\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{ff32}}$, and $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{ff64}}$ for level 6 – 8, and $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{ff32}}$ on level 6.

4.3 Performance benchmarks

For investigation of performance, a more lightweight version of the benchmark used for section 4.2 is used. The setup of this benchmark is described in section 4.1. Runtimes details for the solvers $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{ff32}}$, and $-\dot{\epsilon}_{ff64}$, as well as $IR_{\bar{\epsilon}>\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{ff32}}$ are measured on level 6 – 8. To avoid problems coming from communication, these performance benchmarks are executed on a single core.

Figure 4.6: This figure shows row-wise the relative error in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm (a), the relative residual in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm (b), and the total number of solver iterations (c), per level. Column-wise stopping criterion for the run is given, (I) terminates when either the residual or the error in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm ($\mu_{\|r_h\|} \rightarrow 1 \vee \mu_{\|e\|} \rightarrow 1$) converges. and (II) uses the termination criterion for the performance investigation, which is 1.5 times the total error of $\text{GMG}_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}_{fp64}}$. It contains $\text{IR}_{\bar{\epsilon} > \dot{\epsilon}}$ runs $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32}$, as well as $\text{GMG}_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32}}$, and $\dot{\epsilon}_{fp64}$. The dashed horizontal line represents the total error of $\text{GMG}_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}_{fp64}}$ for the level given in the exponent of the symbol next to the line. The expected convergence rate in big-O notation is given as diagonal dotted line with the relative error in the discrete \tilde{l}^2 -norm of $\text{GMG}_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}_{fp64}}$ on level 1 as line origin. For subfigure IIc point $\text{GMG}_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32}}$ at level 8 needs over 100 iterations and is therefore not visible in this plot.

4.3.1 Time-to-Solution

Solver	N	Time-to-solution (s)			
		Level 6	Level 7	Level 8	Level 9
Pure GMG-64		3.52	2.77×10^1	2.38×10^2	1.99×10^3
IR-64-32	1	5.88	4.83×10^1	4.27×10^2	3.77×10^3
	4	3.17	2.73×10^1	2.39×10^2	1.99×10^3
Pure GMG-32		3.72	1.61×10^2		

Table 4.11: *Time-to-solution*

The expected output for an ideal solver is that the float32 fixed precision GMG is the fastest of the four. Contrary to this assumption, table 4.9 shows that the classical fixed precision GMG solver with the default precision of float64 generally solves the problem the fastest throughout all levels. Only the $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \dot{\epsilon}}_{ff32}$ solver that approximates the residual equation with four inner-solves before updating the approximation to the actual solution $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ is as fast as $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}}_{ff64}$. IR with one inner-solves takes almost twice as long to find a converged solution. Due to additional work being done for IR compared to the pure GMG, it is unlikely that a naive mixed precision approach overpowers the fixed precision one by a factor of two. However, all float32 methods having the same or an even higher runtime as the float64 one is peculiar. As mentioned in section 4.2.3, the influence of the residual on $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}}_{ff32}$ becomes visible from the 6th level onwards. So using mixed precision, additional iterations of the solver compared to $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}}_{ff64}$ are expected at some point. However, this is not expected for the lower resolved benchmarks.

To find out, why the classical fixed precision approach outperforms the mixed precision ones, the timings for some parts of the solver hierarchy described in fig. 4.1 are examined.

4.3.2 Profiling the mixed precision approach

The time-to-solution consists of the time spent solving the problem iteratively (Total Solver Time) and the times to compute the residual and error after each solver iteration. The solver is invoked m times until the quality criteria described in section 4.2.3 is reached. How much time is spent solving the problem can be found in table 4.12. There, the spent time is described as the total time over all iterations, the maximal time per iteration, the average time per iteration, and the number of times the solver is invoked (i.e., the number of iterations).

Table 4.12 indicates even better that the float64 fixed precision solver generally outperforms the others. When comparing only the time spent in the solver, the performance of the mixed precision methods becomes notably worse. On level 7 $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}}_{ff32}$ cannot reach the right solution and the approximation stops after 100

Solver	N	Solver Timings (s)			Invocations
		Total	Max	Average	
Level 6					
Pure GMG-64		2.63	1.66×10^{-1}	1.64×10^{-1}	16
IR-64-32	1	4.99	3.12×10^{-1}	3.12×10^{-1}	16
	4	2.94	7.36×10^{-1}	7.35×10^{-1}	4
Pure GMG-32		2.82	1.82×10^{-1}	1.76×10^{-1}	16
Level 7					
Pure GMG-64		2.04×10^1	1.15	1.13	18
IR-64-32	1	4.09×10^1	2.29	2.27	18
	4	2.52×10^1	5.06	5.04	5
Pure GMG-32		1.21×10^2	1.22	1.20	101
Level 8					
Pure GMG-64		1.74×10^2	8.29	8.27	21
IR-64-32	1	3.62×10^2	1.73×10^1	1.73×10^1	21
	4	2.20×10^2	3.67×10^1	3.67×10^1	6
Pure GMG-32					
Level 9					
Pure GMG-64		1.44×10^3	6.25×10^1	6.25×10^1	23
IR-64-32	1	3.20×10^3	1.33×10^2	1.33×10^2	24
	4	1.85×10^3	3.08×10^2	3.08×10^2	6
Pure GMG-32					

Table 4.12: *Time spent solving the problem.*

iterations. The float32 fixed precision method is still benchmarked to compare the average and maximal values for all parts of the following discussion.

Profiling IR

To find out what part of the solver causes the mixed precision approach to be slower than the fixed precision one, the IR solver is profiled.

IR internally uses N GMG iterations to solve the residual equation eq. (2.26) in ϵ precision. Each time IR is called, one low precision inner-solve loop, one addition to correct the approximation, and one residual computation are performed. The latter two are executed in $\bar{\epsilon}$ precision. Before and after the inner-solve, the residual \mathbf{r}_h is cast to ϵ , and the correction \mathbf{e}_h is cast to $\bar{\epsilon}$, respectively. The timing for each operation can be found in table 4.13.

For the same method, the time spent casting varies notably. The timings for the casting statistics include rounding the precision up for the error correction vector \mathbf{e}_h and rounding down for the residual vector \mathbf{r}_h ; therefore, the number of castings is

twice that of the other operations. The total influence of casting on the runtime is somewhat secondary, though.

Table 4.13 reveals that doing only one iteration per IR invocation to solve the residual equation is, in fact, usually not a good choice. This way, around 20 % of the solver execution is used for the high precision computations instead of `innerSolver`. These high precision computations are not done by the fixed precision solver. To improve the performance compared to pure GMG solver, at least this 20 % of additional runtime must be compensated by reducing the precision of the `innerSolver`. Whether the runtime of the inner-solve can significantly be reduced by using lower precisions is discussed in the next part section 4.3.3.

Finetuning IR

The most obvious observation from table 4.13 is that IR is most beneficial when reducing the additional computations that are not part of the `innerSolver` by increasing the number of iterations N for the inner-solve. However, when increasing the inner-solve iterations, the number of times the low fixed precision solver is called will always be a multiple of N . This behavior is nicely illustrated on level 8 in table 4.12. Both $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp64}}$ and $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32-N=1}}$ invoke their solver 21 times. Therefore, the underlying GMG `innerSolver` is invoked 21 times as well. The $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32}}$ solver using 4 inner-solve iterations $N=4$ is invoked 6 times. So, GMG in the inner-solve is called $4 \cdot 6 = 24$ times. Assuming that the quality of the final approximation depends only on the number of times the `innerSolver` is applied, 3 unnecessary inner-solve iterations are performed; 12.5 % of the `innerSolver` effort are in vain. To put it differently, after 5 invocations, the $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{fp32-N=4}}$ solver barely misses the target accuracy, but is invoked another time anyway; 20 % of the work is repeated for barely improving the outcome. This example should emphasize that tuning the parameters for IR is not as straightforward as it might seem and when solving the LSE is the dominating part of a problem – as for a transport problem – this additional work will slow down a simulation immensely.

So choosing a reasonable number of inner-solve iterations within the IR solver is not as straightforward as hoped. This mixed precision method can be improved by doing parameter studies for the ideal number of inner-solves. A parameter study would be appropriate to finetune a simulation for which solving a problem using IR dominates the computation time. In general, parameter optimization is very problem-specific, though. A more general idea to improve the IR solver could be to make the number of `innerSolver` steps N an adaptive parameter that uses the rate of the residual as an input to adopt N . The adaptive approach is favorable when IR is applied many times within a simulation where the effort of solving the LSE changes; e.g., by changing the problem matrix A and therefore the conditioning $\kappa(A)$ of the problem. In my opinion, the most general way to improve this mixed precision method would be by using IR as a preconditioner for a costly solver. As a preconditioner, a relatively large number of `innerSolver` steps could be chosen with a moderate amount of IR iterations. When

not aiming to solve the problem but improve the initial condition for the used solver, the choice of parameters for IR is not as crucial. This way, the problem is not entirely solved by IR anyway, so a slightly fluctuating number of computations will, in theory, not affect the general performance too much.

4.3.3 Benchmarking the influence of low precision Inner Solve

For both kinds of solving methods, the fixed precision GMG solver², as well as the `innerSolver` for the mixed precision IR solver, a V-cycle with one pre- and post-smoothing step each is executed; i.e., $V(1, 1)$. How much time each solver spends computing V-cycles can be found in table 4.12. The time spent is described as the total time over all iterations, the maximal time per iteration, the average time per iteration, and the total number of times the V-cycle is traversed.

As can be seen from table 4.14, most of the time solving the problem is spent in the V-cycle, therefore, reducing its runtime will improve the performance the most. Reducing the time it takes to compute one V-cycle by reducing the precision is the core idea of this mixed precision approach, as described in section 2.5. Therefore, when analyzing the average time it takes each solver to compute one V-cycle, the fact that the computations done in low precision take even longer than the ones in float64 differs significantly from the expected result. Furthermore, all average timings done in $\epsilon_{f\beta 2}$ are expected to take the same time. Instead, the $IR_{\epsilon > \epsilon - \epsilon_{f\beta 2} - N=1}$ solver takes remarkably longer to compute one V-cycle, while the other three solvers take nearly identical amounts of time. Comparing only the fixed precision methods, the computation in float32 are generally slower than the ones done in float64, which is contrary to what would be expected. Most baffling, however, is the fact that the average time for one V-cycle differs significantly between the two IR solver methods. They vary only by their number of V-cycle N computed before updating the approximation to the solution $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$.

To understand where the large discrepancy between expectation and reality comes from, it is necessary to know how a V-cycle works.

As there is plenty of literature about the properties and structure of a V-cycle [29, 30], this work is only briefly outlining it. A V-cycle consists of two smoothing steps, one restriction, one prolongation, one computation of the residual and one addition for the correction. These computations are done on every grid level except the coarse grid. Instead of performing the parts mentioned above of the solver, a coarse grid solver is invoked.

The same fine grid computations are executed for each solver method. Different timings on the fine grid level would strongly hint at a problem with the implementation. E.g., if some pieces in the low precision computation are still executed in float64, rounding is

²The GMG consists only of this one V-cycle, therefore 100% of the time applying the solver is spent in the V-cycle.

necessary. When rounding is frequently executed, it could slow down the computations immensely. E.g., for the float16 computations executed on hardware that did not inherently support the precision, the total execution took almost three times as long as expected (compare section 3.3). This particular example is most likely not the cause of the increased runtime since the code was tested with the highest compiler verbosity, so implicit casting would lead to an `implicit type conversion` warning. The possibility of a missed software prerequisite for HyTeG is to be kept in mind while continuing the profiling process.

Influence of the coarse grid solver (CG)

The workload between the solver methods can vary for the coarse grid solver, which is the CG (conjugate gradient) solver. As mentioned in section 4.1, the coarse grid is iteratively solved either five times or until the residual on the coarse grid is reduced below the minimal value that can be represented as a normalized number in ϵ precision. Timings for solving the coarse grid can be found in table 4.15.

Solely by looking at the relative influence of the CG algorithm on the solver runtime in table 4.15, it becomes apparent that the coarse grid solver cannot explain the discrepancy described. Furthermore, the coarse grid timings barely differ from each other, neither in total time spent solving the coarse grid, nor in the average time spent for one CG call. Since for all problem resolutions, the coarse grid is solved at grid level 1, the timings of the coarse grid solvers are identical throughout all problem sizes, only the number of CG invocations varies since a higher resolved problem is more complicated to solve and takes more solver iterations.

Since the influence of the coarse grid solve is negligible, it does not cause unexpected timings.

Influence of the smoother (CG)

The smoother is computationally the most expensive part of the V-cycle. The most data points, and therefore the highest amount of work to be done, are on the finest grid Ω_h . The timings spent for smoothing can be found in table 4.16. As before, the levels represent the resolution of the problem. Since only the timings on the finest level are considered, the rows for level i correspond to the fine grid being level i .

The timing values measured for the fine grid smoother coincide with the phenomena observed in tables 4.12 and 4.14. Pre- and post-smoothing are counted together as smoothing since, in this setup, both are identical. Thus, two smoothing steps are performed on each level of the V-cycle, and the number of smoothing invocations is twice the number of V-cycle calls.

According to the MG literature [29, 30], the time spent in a V-cycle cycle is halved for every level of coarsening. The smoother is expected to be the most time-consuming

solver component at each refinement level. This essentially corresponds to the results from table 4.16. Named behavior is less significant for IR than fixed precision GMG due to casting and residual computations. Especially for $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \epsilon - \dot{\epsilon}_{\text{float32}} - N=1}$, where only around 80% of the solver time is employed by the V-cycle (compare table 4.14).

Since the smoothing process consumes a considerable amount of time in the solver, even for $IR_{\bar{\epsilon} > \epsilon - \dot{\epsilon}_{\text{float32}} - N=1}$, as shown in table 4.16, reducing the utilized precision is expected to reduce the time spent on smoothing noticeably. However, the timings of the float32 smooths are relatively close to the timings of the smoothing operations performed in float64. Therefore, no benefit of using mixed precision with HyTeG is found yet.

To understand the gap between expectations and reality, the different parts of the smoother are inspected.

Profiling of the Chebyshev smoother

The smoother used in this setup is the Chebyshev smoother with a polynomial degree of first order. The smoother work can be distributed in three parts: matvec, scaled vector-vector addition, and elementwise vector multiply. In HyTeG, these three operations are `apply`, `assign`, and `multElementwise`, respectively.

The matvec is the computational dominant aspect of the smoother, as seen from table 4.17. Here, the observed times are in line with the expectation. On average, one `apply` on level 9 takes about 13.6s in float64, and only 10s in float32. While this is not the optimal performance increase that can theoretically be achieved when reducing the precision by half (compare section 2.5.3), the total time spent for the matvec is significantly reduced, proving that in general, there is a performance gain when applying mixed precision in HyTeG.

Table 4.17 also reveals that the fact that no runtime reduction is being observed so far stems from the `assign` function. On average, the execution time for `assign` in float32 is six times longer than for float64, while for the `multElementwise`, no noticeable runtime differences between the methods can be observed.

Reason for the poor runtime improvement using mixed precision

The HyTeG function `assign` allows for scaled vector-vector additions. In the Chebyshev smoother, it is used for executing the scaled update of the approximation described in eq. (4.3).

$$\mathbf{e}_h^{n+1} = \mathbf{e}_h^n + \omega D^{-1} (\mathbf{f} - A \mathbf{e}_h^n) \quad (4.3)$$

Where, ω is the precomputed Chebyshev coefficient³ and D^{-1} the precomputed inverse diagonal from the operator matrix A .

³For this numerical experiment the Chebyshev smoother is of first order and therefore, only one coefficient exist.

When searching the source code, it is apparent that the Chebyshev coefficients are stored in float64 precision, which is why the `assign` operation is not only executed in float64 — independent of the `innerSolver` precision — but additional casting operations occur for `innerSolver` of different precision when calculating the scaled addition.

This performance problem should easily be avoided by storing the Chebyshev coefficients in ϵ precision.

When everything is computed in the same precision, the `assign` operation in float32 is executed to compute the scaled vector-vector addition even faster than float64, as it is for `apply`. The reason why the runtime for both operations should be lower when executed in lower precision can be found in section 4.3.4.

The initial assumption for predicting the runtime behavior of a low-precision element-wise multiplication is that the runtime will be reduced, as explained in section 4.3.4. For the HyTeG implementation, however, the timings for this operation are the same for all utilized precisions. While this outcome is not the expected one, the runtime for the low precision implementation is at least not increased and compared to the other two operations within the Chebyshev smoother, the influence of `multElementwise` function is less significant.

In a nutshell, the performance gained by the low precision matvec is cancelled out by the additional casting operations during the scaled vector-vector addition.

Executing the `apply` function on level 9 in float32 instead of float64 saves about 158 s of total runtime. Doing the same for the `assign` function increases the total runtime by around 132 s. So, only approximately 26 s are gained on level 9. Assuming that this behavior is the same throughout all levels, and knowing that for MG half of the compute time is spent on the fine level, currently only about 39 s of smoothing time are saved in the V-cycle by using mixed precision.

The disagreement between expected runtime and actual runtime is, in fact, a software bug that is causing the poor runtime performance for the Chebyshev smoother; i.e., the missed implementation prerequisite to template the coefficients in the Chebyshev smoother.

4.3.4 Possible performance benefits using mixed precision

To estimate the potential computational time savings by reducing the precision of the inner loops without the mentioned casting operations, a simplified best- and worst-case scenario for the scaled vector-vector addition is extrapolated from the results of table 4.17. The best case scenario is that the computational effort of `assign` is reduced by half, so additionally to the 158 s saved on level 9 by `apply`, another 140 s are saved by `assign`; the smoother runtime for float32 is in total reduced by 298 s on level 9 and 447 s in total on all levels. While the worst case is that no runtime is saved

and the `assign` function in float32 takes as long to compute as in float64; only the measured 158 s for `apply` on the finest grid and 237 s in total are saved compared to $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{ff64}}$.

Using IR as mixed precision solver for this problem, additional operations are added by the solver, as mentioned in section 2.5.2. Using the measurements from table 4.13 for level 9, the two solver configurations add another 625 s of work when using only one inner-solve, and 119 s doing four inner-solves. According to table 4.12, float64 GMG takes 1440 s to solve the problem on level 9. Assuming that only the additional work from IR and the saved work from the low precision Chebyshev smoother influence the total solver runtime compared to the fixed precision solver, the resulting runtime changes are:

Scenario	N	Δt	$T_0 + \Delta t$
		Runtime change (s)	New net runtime (s)
Best case	1	+178	1618
	4	-328	1112
Worst case	1	+388	1828
	4	-118	1322

Comparing these runtime changes with the total $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\dot{\epsilon}-\dot{\epsilon}_{ff64}}$ solver runtime T_0 from table 4.12, the new net solver time would, in the best case, change to 112.36 % ($N=1$), or 77.22 % ($N=4$) of the original value T_0 ; or, in the worst-case scenario, to 126.94 % ($N=1$), or 91.18 % ($N=4$) from T_0 ; These proportional changes are computed according to eq. (4.4),

$$\frac{T_0 + \Delta t}{T_0} \tag{4.4}$$

where T_0 is the solver runtime of GMG in float64 precision on level 9 as measured in table 4.12 and Δt is the net runtime change noted in the table above.

Through this thought experiment, two valuable insights can be deduced. Firstly, by effectively implementing and optimizing mixed precision, performance can be significantly boosted. Secondly, selecting a suitable parameter for IR is essential, as mentioned in section 4.3.2.

Profiling matvec

The matvec is generated using HOG with the optimizations described in section 4.1.

To further increase the performance of the mixed precision implementation in HyTeG, the most dominant computation within the discussed solvers is analyzed, i.e., the matvec.

According to table 4.17, when reducing the precision from 64 bit to 32 bit, the compute time for one matvec is reduced to about three quarters of the one from fixed precision

$GMG_{\tilde{\epsilon}=\tilde{\epsilon}_{ff64}}$. In theory, reducing the time by one-half should be possible. For determining whether this is possible in HyTeG, the subroutines of the `apply` function used in the Chebyshev smoother on the finest grid are analyzed. These subroutines are, the `kernel` execution, `pre-communication` and `post-communication`, an `Interpolate` function and some miscellaneous computations that are summarized as `Remainder`.

The working horse of the `apply` function is the `kernel` with 40% to 60% of the time used for a matvec and 10% to 26% of the entire solver. When executed in $\tilde{\epsilon}_{ff32}$, the average compute time is roughly halved compared to $\tilde{\epsilon}_{ff64}$. This is already the theoretical optimal performance improvement that can be achieved by reducing the precision.

In terms of dominance within the matvec, the next highest part is the `Remainder`. To find out if this part can be optimized for mixed precision, more specific timing is necessary, as it is mainly assumed to be runtime control, and integer computations for addresses the `Remainder` is not examined by this thesis.

This function uses the `Interpolation` part to set the destination array to zero. The average runtime for both precisions is identical. Since setting an array to zero consists solely of store instructions, further investigations in low precision store vector intrinsics could reduce its runtime by half. As this store instruction only accounts for 5% to 8% of the total solver runtime, the expected effort-to-outcome ratio for this optimization is unrewarding.

The last subroutine of the matvec is the communication. Currently, the influence of communication is low. However, these benchmarks are all performed using a single node. The runtime behavior of the communication routines should be considered when scaling experiments using mixed precision, though. In HPC, problems are usually huge, so it is common practice to distribute work onto several machines. When doing so, performance often becomes limited by communication, so mixed precision, which reduces the data traffic size, can be a profitable optimization for highly scalable problems. However, the runtime results for communication in table 4.18 suggest that it is not adequately implemented for using different data sizes. For `post-communication`, the average runtimes between the different precisions are identical. As it is unclear what `post-communication` does — other than filling the halo layers — it cannot be said whether the implementation can be improved without performing distributed computations. For `pre-communication`, however, the average runtime in float32 is about three times as high as for float64, which strongly hints to additional casting that is being performed, as it is the case for the `assign` (compare section 4.3.3). If this is the case, removing the casting operation is probably an easy task that will likely significantly improve future scaling investigations.

Figure 4.7: Exemplary roofline of fig. 2.9 adjusted to section 4.3.4. For low, and high precision float32, and float64 are respectively inserted. Furthermore, the figure is extended for the case of level 6, where it is assumed, that neither the compute-bound nor the memory-bound is reached yet.

Roofline demonstration

Considering the problem in a roofline model [11]. An schematic roofline plot for a matvec is given in fig. 4.7. As the figure illustrates, a matvec is usually a memory-bound computation. Here, the data transfer size per operation is reduced from 8 B to 4 B ($I_{\text{fp64}} \rightarrow I_{\text{fp32}}$).

The fact that the influence on average runtime per matvec is more significant for higher resolution stems from the fact that for lower levels, the hardware is not saturated; i.e., the performance bound is not met. This case is also visualized in fig. 4.7. The dots on the vertical code intensity line stand for the achieved performance P_{lv16} for small problem sizes; e.g., level 6.

The explanation on the roofline plot should emphasize the benefit of using mixed precision, which can be observed from the results of table 4.18.

Part	Timings (s)			Invo- cations	Effort ratio (%)
	Total	Max	Average		
level 6					
$N=1$					
Copying-Casting	2.15×10^{-1}	9.39×10^{-3}	6.71×10^{-3}	32	4.31
Residual-Computation	7.73×10^{-1}	4.84×10^{-2}	4.83×10^{-2}	16	15.50
Inner-Loop	3.98	2.49×10^{-1}	2.49×10^{-1}	16	79.80
$N=4$					
Copying-Casting	5.34×10^{-2}	9.16×10^{-3}	6.67×10^{-3}	8	1.81
Residual-Computation	1.46×10^{-1}	3.68×10^{-2}	3.66×10^{-2}	4	4.97
Inner-Loop	2.74	6.85×10^{-1}	6.84×10^{-1}	4	93.04
level 7					
$N=1$					
Copying-Casting	1.68	6.75×10^{-2}	4.67×10^{-2}	36	4.10
Residual-Computation	6.41	3.64×10^{-1}	3.56×10^{-1}	18	15.65
Inner-Loop	3.27×10^1	1.82	1.82	18	79.86
$N=4$					
Copying-Casting	4.78×10^{-1}	6.38×10^{-2}	4.78×10^{-2}	10	1.90
Residual-Computation	1.29	2.58×10^{-1}	2.58×10^{-1}	5	5.12
Inner-Loop	2.34×10^1	4.70	4.68	5	92.80
level 8					
$N=1$					
Copying-Casting	1.45×10^1	4.87×10^{-1}	3.46×10^{-1}	42	4.01
Residual-Computation	5.65×10^1	2.70	2.69	21	15.58
Inner-Loop	2.90×10^2	1.38×10^1	1.38×10^1	21	80.02
$N=4$					
Copying-Casting	4.36	5.22×10^{-1}	3.63×10^{-1}	12	1.98
Residual-Computation	1.14×10^1	1.90	1.89	6	5.16
Inner-Loop	2.04×10^2	3.40×10^1	3.40×10^1	6	92.67
level 9					
$N=1$					
Copying-Casting	1.29×10^2	3.75	2.68	48	4.02
Residual-Computation	4.96×10^2	2.07×10^1	2.07×10^1	24	15.51
Inner-Loop	2.56×10^3	1.07×10^2	1.07×10^2	24	80.07
$N=4$					
Copying-Casting	3.27×10^1	3.86	2.72	12	1.77
Residual-Computation	8.60×10^1	1.43×10^1	1.43×10^1	6	4.66
Inner-Loop	1.72×10^3	2.87×10^2	2.87×10^2	6	93.40

Table 4.13: Timings of the IR solver.

Solver	N	Timings (s)			Invocations	Effort ratio to Solver (%)
		Total	Max	Average		
Level 6						
Pure GMG-64		2.63	1.66×10^{-1}	1.64×10^{-1}	16	100.00
IR-64-32	1	3.98	2.49×10^{-1}	2.49×10^{-1}	16	79.78
	4	2.74	1.75×10^{-1}	1.71×10^{-1}	16	93.04
Pure GMG-32		2.82	1.82×10^{-1}	1.76×10^{-1}	16	100.00
Level 7						
Pure GMG-64		2.04×10^1	1.15	1.13	18	100.00
IR-64-32	1	3.27×10^1	1.82	1.82	18	79.86
	4	2.34×10^1	1.18	1.17	20	92.80
Pure GMG-32		1.21×10^2	1.22	1.20	101	100.00
Level 8						
Pure GMG-64		1.74×10^2	8.29	8.27	21	100.00
IR-64-32	1	2.90×10^2	1.38×10^1	1.38×10^1	21	80.02
	4	2.04×10^2	8.57	8.50	24	92.67
Pure GMG-32						
Level 9						
Pure GMG-64		1.44×10^3	6.25×10^1	6.25×10^1	23	100.00
IR-64-32	1	2.56×10^3	1.07×10^2	1.07×10^2	24	80.07
	4	1.72×10^3	7.19×10^1	7.18×10^1	24	93.40
Pure GMG-32						

Table 4.14: *Timings for computing V-cycles.*

Solver	N	Solver Timings (s)			Invocations	Effort ratio to Solver (%)
		Total	Max	Average		
Level 6						
Pure GMG-64		2.47×10^{-2}	1.58×10^{-3}	1.54×10^{-3}	16	0.94
IR-64-32	1	2.54×10^{-2}	1.62×10^{-3}	1.59×10^{-3}	16	0.51
	4	2.23×10^{-2}	1.63×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-3}	16	0.76
Pure GMG-32		2.55×10^{-2}	1.64×10^{-3}	1.59×10^{-3}	16	0.90
Level 7						
Pure GMG-64		2.77×10^{-2}	1.58×10^{-3}	1.54×10^{-3}	18	0.14
IR-64-32	1	2.86×10^{-2}	1.64×10^{-3}	1.59×10^{-3}	18	0.07
	4	2.79×10^{-2}	1.61×10^{-3}	1.40×10^{-3}	20	0.11
Pure GMG-32		1.60×10^{-1}	1.63×10^{-3}	1.58×10^{-3}	101	0.13
Level 8						
Pure GMG-64		3.27×10^{-2}	1.65×10^{-3}	1.56×10^{-3}	21	0.02
IR-64-32	1	3.41×10^{-2}	1.67×10^{-3}	1.62×10^{-3}	21	0.01
	4	3.39×10^{-2}	1.61×10^{-3}	1.41×10^{-3}	24	0.02
Pure GMG-32						
Level 9						
Pure GMG-64		3.68×10^{-2}	1.63×10^{-3}	1.60×10^{-3}	23	0.00
IR-64-32	1	3.97×10^{-2}	1.67×10^{-3}	1.65×10^{-3}	24	0.00
	4	3.54×10^{-2}	1.66×10^{-3}	1.47×10^{-3}	24	0.00
Pure GMG-32						

Table 4.15: *Timings spent in the coarse grid solver (CG).*

4 Numerical Experiment

Solver	N	Absolute Smoother Timings (s)			Invocations	Relative to (%)	
		Total	Max	Average		Fine lvl	Solver
Level 6							
Pure GMG-64		1.34	4.47×10^{-2}	4.19×10^{-2}	32	61.98	50.41
IR-64-32	1	1.46	4.95×10^{-2}	4.58×10^{-2}	32	59.64	38.17
	4	1.43	4.62×10^{-2}	4.47×10^{-2}	32	59.43	45.49
Pure GMG-32		1.44	4.57×10^{-2}	4.51×10^{-2}	32	64.19	51.68
Level 7							
Pure GMG-64		1.10×10^1	3.10×10^{-1}	3.07×10^{-1}	36	63.33	54.13
IR-64-32	1	1.19×10^1	3.36×10^{-1}	3.32×10^{-1}	36	60.17	40.39
	4	1.32×10^1	3.35×10^{-1}	3.29×10^{-1}	40	60.00	48.15
Pure GMG-32		6.71×10^1	3.41×10^{-1}	3.32×10^{-1}	202	65.86	56.14
Level 8							
Pure GMG-64		9.65×10^1	2.32	2.30	42	64.31	55.49
IR-64-32	1	1.04×10^2	2.50	2.48	42	60.38	40.92
	4	1.19×10^2	2.50	2.48	48	60.47	48.97
Pure GMG-32							
Level 9							
Pure GMG-64		8.05×10^2	1.75×10^1	1.75×10^1	46	65.17	56.44
IR-64-32	1	8.64×10^2	1.88×10^1	1.88×10^1	46	68.10	44.30
	4	9.00×10^2	1.88×10^1	1.88×10^1	48	68.08	54.39
Pure GMG-32							

Table 4.16: *Timings spent smoothing the fine grid using the Chebyshev smoother.*

Part	N	Absolute Timings (s)			Invocations	Relative to (%)	
		Total	Max	Average		Smoother	Solver
apply							
Pure GMG-64		6.28×10^2	1.37×10^1	1.36×10^1	46	77.97	44.00
IR-64-32- $N=1$	1	4.60×10^2	1.00×10^1	1.00×10^1	46	53.32	23.62
IR-64-32- $N=4$	4	4.80×10^2	1.00×10^1	1.00×10^1	48	53.31	29.00
assign							
Pure GMG-64		4.77×10^1	5.25×10^{-1}	5.18×10^{-1}	92	5.92	3.34
IR-64-32- $N=1$	1	2.75×10^2	3.00	2.98	92	31.79	14.08
IR-64-32- $N=4$	4	2.86×10^2	3.00	2.98	96	31.79	17.29
elementwise-multiply							
Pure GMG-64		1.30×10^2	2.83	2.82	46	16.11	9.09
IR-64-32- $N=1$	1	1.29×10^2	2.81	2.80	46	14.90	6.60
IR-64-32- $N=4$	4	1.34×10^2	2.80	2.79	48	14.89	8.10

Table 4.17: *Timings Chebyshev smoother. All measurements are done at level 9, with the finest grid Ω_h being on this level.*

Solver	N	Absolute Timings (s)			Invocations	Relative to (%)	
		Total	Max	Average		HOG-apply	Solver
kernel							
Pure GMG-64		3.66×10^2	3.43×10^{-1}	3.31×10^{-1}	1104	58.29	25.65
IR-64-32	1	1.92×10^2	1.84×10^{-1}	1.74×10^{-1}	1104	41.74	9.86
IR-64-32	4	2.00×10^2	1.78×10^{-1}	1.74×10^{-1}	1152	41.75	12.11
pre-communication							
Pure GMG-64		5.64	1.24×10^{-1}	1.23×10^{-1}	46	0.90	0.40
IR-64-32	1	1.81×10^1	4.01×10^{-1}	3.93×10^{-1}	46	3.92	0.93
IR-64-32	4	1.89×10^1	4.00×10^{-1}	3.94×10^{-1}	48	3.94	1.14
post-communication							
Pure GMG-64		1.08×10^1	2.39×10^{-1}	2.34×10^{-1}	46	1.71	0.75
IR-64-32	1	9.97	2.25×10^{-1}	2.17×10^{-1}	46	2.17	0.51
IR-64-32	4	1.05×10^1	2.23×10^{-1}	2.18×10^{-1}	48	2.18	0.63
Interpolate							
Pure GMG-64		1.11×10^2	2.42	2.42	46	17.69	7.78
IR-64-32	1	1.08×10^2	2.36	2.35	46	23.52	5.56
IR-64-32	4	1.13×10^2	2.36	2.35	48	23.48	6.81
Remainder							
Pure GMG-64		1.34×10^2			1	21.41	9.42
IR-64-32	1	1.32×10^2			1	28.64	6.77
IR-64-32	4	1.38×10^2			1	28.66	8.31

Table 4.18: *Timings for the HOG generated `apply` function used for the matvecs computations within the Chebyshev smoother. All measurements are done at level 9, with the finest grid Ω_h being on this level. Interpolate is used to set the destination array to zero.*

The HPC framework HyTeG was successfully extended for the use of mixed precision.

Implementation Mixed precision can be utilized for \mathbb{P}_1 elements with the GMG solver, the CG solver, the Chebyshev smoother, and the newly implemented IR solver. This is possible by generating typed operators with HOG. In theory, it is possible to generate operators of any type, but correctness is tested for float16, float32, and float64 only. How to use mixed precision in HyTeG is explained in section 3.2.

The MPFR library is included in HyTeG, but the resulting performance is insufficient for the requirements of this thesis, thus, precisions higher than float64 are not pursued further.

Investigations for float16 revealed that, currently, only the GNU compiler with a minimal version of 13 supports float16 on CPUs, and that Intel's Sapphire Rapid Generation CPUs support fast float16 implementations. This was confirmed by running benchmarks on the Fritz computing cluster from NHR@FAU where a significant performance increase for float16 was demonstrated compared to float32 and float64 (section 3.3).

Quality of mixed precision The implemented IR algorithm according to Tamstorf et al. [4] was tested by approximating the solution of a 3D Poisson Equation with a linear discretization on 24 macro elements. The results from this mixed precision approach were compared to a float64 fixed precision approximation regarding accuracy and performance.

Accuracy For a \mathbb{P}_1 discretization it is confirmed that the mixed precision implementation in HyTeG works and converges with the expected rate of $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$.

For coarser refinements, even utilizing a fixed precision method in float32 is sufficient up to 8.48×10^6 DoFs at refinement level 9 in 3D. When used with IR, float32 could be used as solver precision for all resolutions within the given main memory limitation,

when its residual is computed in float64 without compromising accuracy in comparison to a fixed precision GMG solver in float64. So, the range of applicability for float32 could be expanded using IR. This aligns with the findings by Tamstorf et al. [4].

The same solver approach could be utilized for lower precisions as well, i.e., float16 solver precision. Correct approximations could be produced for a resolution of up to 2.45×10^3 DoFs at refinement level 3 in 3D. The float16 fixed precision GMG produced correct results for the same level. Therefore, for float16, the same mixed precision approach yields no benefits compared to the fixed precision one.

Performance The runtime performance of mixed precision IR with float32 `innerSolver` precision and float64 `residual compute` precision was compared to fixed precision GMG in float64. Both solvers were iteratively executed until the accuracy of the approximation reached 1.5 times the discretization error. The time-to-solution for both methods was comparable, which does not match the expected result. Upon profiling the runtimes for the solver hierarchy, it was discovered that a significant number of casting operations occurs during a scaled vector-vector addition. Further investigation revealed that this issue stemmed from a missing type-templating within one of the core solvers.

Insights regarding possible performance optimizations were gained by analyzing the profiling output. Firstly, the number of `innerSolver` iterations for IR significantly impacts the overall runtime. Secondly, reducing the precision for the matrix-vector multiplication by half results in a roughly 50% decrease in runtime, which aligns closely with the theoretical optimum. Finally, based on extrapolating the runtime measurements, the prediction was made that without fine-tuning or additional optimizations, but including the mentioned missing templating, the time-to-solution would increase to 127% or decrease to 77% of the float64 fixed precision implementation in the worst-case and best-case scenarios, respectively.

In conclusion, the mixed precision extension for HyTeG works, and it supports float16, float32, and float64 on a \mathbb{P}_1 discretization and type-generated operators. Accurate results are achieved, but there is still potential for performance optimization.

Topics for future work

- Reevaluating the performance investigations after including the missing type-templating.
- Extending the mixed precision support to other FE spaces, e.g., \mathbb{P}_2 to allow the approximation of more complex problems like the Stokes equation.
- Modifying the IR `innerSolver` to allow for a more applicable use of float16; e.g., using float16 only for some matrix-vector multiplications.
- Utilizing the MPI extension for float16 by performing multinode scaling runs with the IR solver.

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